

Inherit

INHERIT pilots' execution documentation – full pilot operation phase / D5.3

WP 5, T 5.2, T 5.3, T5.4 & T5.5

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
APIKAM	Ahmet Piriştina City Archive and Museum
AR	Augmented Reality
BIM	Building Information Model
CH	Cultural Heritage
D	Deliverable
DT	Digital Twin
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
EU	European Union
GIS	Geographic Information System
H-BIM	Heritage/Historic Building Information Model
IEQ	Indoor Environmental Quality
IoT	Internet of Things
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MCDA	Multiple-Criteria Decision Analysis
MSF	Multi-Stakeholder Forum
NEB	New European Bauhaus
OODs	Owners, Operators, and Decision-makers
Q	Quarter
Q&A	Questions and Answers
S.x	Service
SL	Social Labs
S-LCA	Social Life Cycle Assessment
SOAR	Strengths, Opportunities, Aspirations, Results
SSID	Service Set Identifier

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T	Task
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
VR	Virtual Reality
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

The INHERIT project aims to develop sustainable and inclusive approaches to managing cultural heritage by employing a systematic methodology that integrates advanced technologies with socially and behaviourally informed practices. Through this integration, the project aims to create tailored interventions that not only enhance energy efficiency and sustainability but also safeguard the cultural significance of heritage sites. These solutions, or services as they will be referenced across this report, are designed to be scalable and economically viable, with applications across different pilot sites in Europe.

This deliverable is the continuation of D5.2- **INHERIT pilots' execution documentation – pre-pilot & operation phase**, which documented the preparatory and operational planning phase of the pilots. D5.3 reports on the **full deployment phase**, marking the transition from framework design to real-life execution. It captures the implementation of INHERIT services under real operational conditions across the eight pilot sites, reflecting diverse climatic zones, governance structures, heritage typologies and institutional contexts.

The full deployment phase revealed varying levels of technical readiness, data availability and organisational capacity across pilots. Services progressed at different speeds, ranging from configuration and demonstration to testing and continuous operational use. To manage this heterogeneity, a structured cross-pilot monitoring framework was applied, supported by iterative data collection rounds, targeted coordination actions and reinforced communication between pilots, service providers and WP5 leadership. This approach ensured transparency in tracking deployment status, identifying bottlenecks and realigning implementation timelines where necessary.

In parallel, stakeholder engagement activities moved from planning to operational implementation. Social Labs, Multi-Stakeholder Forum (MSF) events, co-creation workshops, and continuous dialogue mechanisms facilitated structured interaction among end-users, administrators, policymakers and cultural heritage professionals. These activities supported alignment between technical development and user expectations, while strengthening institutional ownership and social acceptance of the services.

From an evaluation perspective, D5.3 constitutes the interim application phase of the Evaluation and Impact Assessment Framework established in D5.2. As quantitative performance data are not yet fully consolidated across all pilots, emphasis during this stage was placed on structured qualitative assessment. A SOAR (Strengths, Opportunities, Aspirations, Results) analysis was implemented to systematically capture pilot expectations, perceived added value, and anticipated impacts of each service. The SOAR outcomes provide a qualitative benchmark that will inform the comparative assessment of realised performance in Deliverable **D5.4 – INHERIT impact & social acceptance analysis**.

Finally, early observations relevant to replication indicate that service transferability is influenced by contextual factors such as regulatory frameworks, climatic conditions, data quality, building characteristics and user practices. The deployment experience therefore contributes not only to service validation but also to refining the replication roadmap toward broader European Union (EU)-level uptake.

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Overall, D5.3 documents the operationalisation of the INHERIT framework in practice, validates the coordination and monitoring mechanisms established in the preparatory phase and establishes the analytical basis for the final validation and consolidated impact assessment to be presented in D5.4.

1. Introduction

1.1. Background

The INHERIT project addresses the need to reconcile cultural heritage preservation with energy efficiency, sustainability and climate adaptation objectives. Building upon the preparatory and operational planning documented in Deliverable **D5.2 – INHERIT pilots' execution documentation – pre-pilot & operation phase¹**, the present deliverable reports on the **full pilot operation phase**, during which INHERIT services were deployed under real-life conditions across eight European pilot sites.

Within WP5, “*Demonstration of INHERIT towards sustainable and resilient Cultural Heritage,*” the deployment phase represents a critical transition from design and readiness assessment to execution, coordination and early validation. Pilots function as living laboratories, testing INHERIT’s digital and decision-support services in diverse contexts that vary in building typology, climate zone, governance structures, digital maturity and stakeholder ecosystems.

The shift from planning to execution revealed practical constraints not fully observable during the preparatory stage, including infrastructure limitations, data gaps, procurement delays, regulatory considerations and uneven levels of organisational readiness. At the same time, it confirmed the relevance of the coordination and monitoring framework established in D5.2, while highlighting the need for reinforced pilot activation and iterative monitoring.

D5.3 therefore documents not only what has been implemented, but also how deployment unfolded in practice, how coordination mechanisms functioned and how services were perceived during early operational use.

1.2. Objectives of the deliverable

The objective of Deliverable D5.3 is to provide a structured documentation and interim assessment of the INHERIT full deployment phase. Specifically, it aims to:

- Present the operational status and progress of service deployment across all pilots,
- Document cross-pilot coordination mechanisms and monitoring practices,
- Capture observed challenges, technical constraints and corrective actions,
- Report on stakeholder engagement activities implemented during deployment,
- Consolidate qualitative insights through the SOAR analysis as an interim evaluation benchmark,
- Identify early observations relevant for service replication and scaling.

This deliverable represents the intermediate stage in the WP5 continuum:

- D5.2 established the framework and readiness conditions,
- D5.3 documents deployment and interim assessment,
- D5.4 will consolidate validated performance results and social acceptance outcomes.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/18184836>

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1.3. Structure of the report

The report is structured to reflect the logical progression from deployment execution to evaluation and replication considerations:

- **Section 2** presents the operational status and progress of each pilot, including services implemented, deployment actions and observed challenges.
- **Section 3** reports on stakeholder collaboration during the full deployment phase, including workshops, MSF activities, continuous support mechanisms and user scenario development.
- **Section 4** provides a cross-pilot overview of deployment coordination, monitoring structures, feedback loops and readiness toward final validation.
- **Section 5** presents the interim Evaluation & Impact Assessment progress, including the structured SOAR analysis, its methodological approach and preliminary results.
- **Section 6** outlines initial replication activities, early findings and next steps toward a structured replication roadmap.

This structure ensures a coherent narrative from operational execution to strategic reflection, maintaining continuity with D5.2 while preparing the analytical foundation for D5.4.

2. Pilot Operation Status & Progress

This section presents the progress of service implementation across the INHERIT pilot sites during the full operation phase. For each pilot, an overview table summarises the services being deployed and their current testing and usage status. This is followed by a short description of the implementation progress for each service, including key operational steps undertaken and the main challenges or considerations identified by the pilots during deployment. Together, these sections provide a consolidated overview of the current status of service implementation across the demonstration sites.

2.1. Pilot 1- Jastrebarsko, Croatia

2.1.1. Services Implemented During Full Operation Phase

Table 1 Services to be Implemented in Pilot 1 and their implementation status

Services to be implemented in Pilot 1	Testing Status	Use	Users	Current Use
Service 0: Smartification & Data Exchange Platform	Not Started	Ad-hoc	Admin Users	The service is being prepared for testing and use after March 2026.
Service 3: Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	Testing started in Quarter (Q)1 2026	Ad-hoc	Admin Users	The service is being prepared for testing and use in early-to-mid 2026. It is intended to compare alternative renovation scenarios and support medium- to long-term strategic decision-making related to building upgrades. It has been demonstrated to the pilot and now testing with the stakeholders will follow.
Service 4: Indoor environmental quality and comfort optimisation	Testing started in Q3 2025	Continuous	Admin Users	Continuous monitoring of indoor environmental quality (IEQ) parameters. The service supports periodic operational adjustments aimed at improving thermal comfort and overall indoor conditions during daily operation.
Service 5: Energy forecasting and data-driven intelligent management	Testing started in Q4 2025	Ad-hoc	Admin Users	The service will be used to monitor energy consumption trends and support forecasting activities, informing energy management decisions during the operational phase.
Service 10: Heritage building environmental climate scenarios	Not Started	Ad-hoc	Admin Users	The service has not been activated or used during the full pilot operation phase. At this stage, the service remains under development by the service provider, and no testing or operational

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					<p>activities have been carried out at the pilot site. Use of service is predicted for April 2026.</p>
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2.1.2. Progress During Full Operation Phase

During the full operation phase, deployment activities for **Pilot 1** progressed across all planned services at varying levels of maturity. For **Service 0 (Smartification & Data Exchange Platform)**, development activities were carried out during this period, with a demonstration of the service and pilot training foreseen for the first quarter of 2026.

Regarding **Service 3 (Decision Support Tool for Optimal Renovation Planning)**, configuration and parameter adjustments were undertaken in close operational coordination with the service provider. A first demonstration of the tool was completed in January 2026, while broader testing activities involving stakeholders were scheduled in February 2026 and feedback was given to the service providers.

Service 4 (IEQ and thermal comfort optimization) advanced to a more mature stage, including configuration and parameter fine-tuning, testing sessions under real operational conditions, and the establishment of continuous data collection. These activities were supported by ongoing coordination with the service provider to ensure stable operation.

For **Service 5 (Energy Forecasting and Intelligent Management)**, configuration and adjustment activities were implemented, alongside the initiation of data collection under real operational conditions. Operational coordination with the service provider was maintained, and a service demonstration was completed in January 2026, where pilot partners provided their feedback to the service provider.

Finally, for **Service 10 (Heritage Buildings Environmental Climate Scenarios)**, configuration and parameter adjustment activities were initiated and pilot-specific data were provided to support service development. A demonstration of the service is currently foreseen for April 2026.

2.1.3. Observed Challenges During Operation

Table 2 Challenges identified during service operation by Pilot 1

Services to be implemented in Pilot 1	Challenges Observed
Service 0: Smartification & Data Exchange Platform	No operational challenges identified to date.
Service 3: Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	No operational challenges identified to date.
Service 4: Indoor environmental quality and comfort optimisation	No operational challenges identified to date, service is fully operational and data is collected continuously.
Service 5: Energy forecasting and data-driven intelligent management	No operational challenges identified to date.
Service 10: Heritage building environmental climate scenarios	No operational challenges identified to date, as testing the use of service is scheduled to begin in April 2026.

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2.2. Pilot 2 – Noisiel, France

2.2.1. Services Implemented During Full Operation Phase

Table 3 Services to be Implemented in Pilot 2 and their implementation status

Services to be implemented in Pilot 2	Testing Status	Use	Users	Current Use
Service 0: Smartification & Data Exchange	Not Started	Ad-hoc	Admin Users	The service is being prepared for testing and use by Q1 2026.
Service 2: Modelling and simulation environment	Testing started in Q1 2026	Ad-hoc	End Users	Service under development. Pilot data submitted (June 2025). Awaiting delivery of building model to initiate scenario testing.
Service 3: Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	Testing started in Q1 2026	Ad-hoc	End Users	Initial tool presentation completed (January 2026). Data entry initiated by three end-users; feedback pending.
Service 4: Indoor environmental quality and comfort optimisation	Abandoned	--	--	Assessing comfort criteria is currently unnecessary as the building remains vacant. Additionally, the building's transformation and renovation works are not expected to be finalized within the Inherit project's timeframe.

2.2.2. Progress During Full Operation Phase

During the full deployment phase, activities in **Pilot 2** focused on Services 2 and 3.

For **Service 2 (Modelling and Simulation Environment)**, the service remains under construction. Data inputs were provided by the pilot in June 2025 to support model development, and the pilot is currently awaiting delivery of the building model in order to proceed with testing. The service is intended to compare alternative renovation scenarios for the BYCN design team.

For **Service 3 (Decision Support Tool for Optimal Renovation Planning)**, a presentation of the tool was conducted by the service provider in January 2026. Three end-users have initiated the process of filling in the Excel-based tool, and feedback is expected following this initial testing phase.

2.2.3. Observed Challenges During Operation

Table 4 Challenges identified during service operation by Pilot 2

Services to be implemented in Pilot 2	Challenges Observed
Service 0: Smartification & Data Exchange Platform	No operational challenges identified to date.

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Service 2: Modelling and simulation environment	No operational challenges identified to date.
Service 3: Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	No operational challenges identified to date.

2.3. Pilot 3 - Athens, Greece

2.3.1. Services Implemented During Full Operation Phase

Table 5 Services to be Implemented in Pilot 3 and their implementation status

Services to be implemented in Pilot 3	Testing Status	Use	Users	Current Use
Service 0: Smartification & Data Exchange Platform	Not Started	Ad-hoc	Admin Users	The service is being prepared for testing and use by Q1 2026.
Service 3: Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	Testing started in Q1 2026	Ad-hoc (confirmation with the service provider is required)	Admin Users	The service is being prepared for testing and use in early 2026. It is intended to compare alternative renovation scenarios and support medium-to long-term strategic decision-making related to building upgrades.
Service 4: Indoor environmental quality and comfort optimisation	Testing started in Q3 2025	Continuous	Admin users; indirect impact on end-users	Continuous monitoring of IEQ parameters. The service supports periodic operational adjustments aimed at improving thermal comfort and overall indoor conditions during daily operation.
Service 5: Energy Forecasting & Data-Driven Intelligence Management	Testing started in Q4 2025	Regular	Admin users, energy managers	The service is used to monitor energy consumption trends and support forecasting activities, informing energy management decisions during the operational phase.
Service 7: Real-Time Insights on Activity and Mobility Patterns	Testing started in Q4 2025	Continuous	Admin users	Data are analysed periodically to understand space utilisation and visitor flow patterns, supporting operational optimisation and longer-term planning considerations.
Service 9: GIS-Based Solution for Sustainable	Testing started in Q4 2025	Ad-hoc	Admin users	The service is used as a reference tool to cluster historical building assets, visualise their spatial

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Heritage Maintenance					distribution, and monitor maintenance status to support informed decision-making.
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2.3.2. Progress During Full Operation Phase

During the full deployment phase, **Pilot 3** advanced multiple services under real operational conditions.

For **Service 0 (Smartification & Data Exchange Platform)**, the responsible service provider reported ongoing development, with a demonstration provisionally planned for within Spring 2026 and subject to confirmation.

For **Service 3 (Decision Support Tool for Optimal Renovation Planning)**, user sessions and testing activities are taking place within Spring 2026 as part of the structured deployment process.

Service 4 (Indoor Environmental Quality and Thermal Comfort Optimisation) progressed through configuration and parameter adjustment, followed by testing sessions under real operational conditions. Continuous data collection was established, supported by user onboarding for administrative users and ongoing operational coordination with the service provider.

For **Service 5 (Energy Forecasting and Intelligent Management)**, configuration and adjustment activities were completed, alongside testing sessions and the initiation of data collection under real operational conditions. User onboarding and coordination with the service provider supported the transition toward regular operational use.

Service 7 (Real-Time Insights on Activity and Mobility Patterns) underwent configuration and adjustment, followed by testing sessions. Data collection under real operational conditions was initiated at the end of December 2025, with continued coordination with the service provider.

Finally, **Service 9 (GIS-Based Solution for Sustainable Heritage Maintenance)** progressed through configuration and adjustment, testing sessions, and data collection under real operational conditions. User onboarding and operational coordination with the service provider were also carried out to support implementation.

2.3.3. Observed Challenges During Operation

Table 6 Challenges identified during service operation by Pilot 3

Services to be implemented in Pilot 3	Challenges Observed
Service 0: Smartification & Data Exchange Platform	No operational challenges identified to date, as testing sessions are scheduled to begin in March 2026.
Service 3: Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	No operational challenges identified to date, as testing sessions are scheduled to begin in January 2026.
Service 4: Indoor environmental quality and comfort optimisation	<p>Feasibility issues: in installing thermostatic heads due to the old and fragile building infrastructure. Maintenance and heating system installation activities were completed by mid-March 2026. In the ELLET building, thermostatic heads are intended to improve the regulation of heat distribution across spaces with different day-to-day uses, in line with</p>

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	<p>ELLET's broader aim of achieving better thermal comfort and more efficient system operation through compatible upgrades.</p> <p>Technical issues: Temporary data gaps occurred due to sensor battery depletion. Following coordination with the service provider, the introduction of a battery monitoring tool was recommended.</p>
<p>Service 5: Energy Forecasting & Data-Driven Intelligence Management</p>	<p>Feasibility and technical issues: Similar challenges to those identified for service 4, mainly related to infrastructure constraints and temporary data gaps caused by sensor battery exhaustion. The pilot therefore required additional technical work to restore sensor operation and ensure a sufficiently robust and reliable dataset for monitoring purposes.</p>
<p>Service 7: Real-Time Insights on Activity and Mobility Patterns</p>	<p>Technical issues: Initial data accuracy issues were identified due to overlapping sensor coverage zones. These were resolved in coordination with the service provider.</p>
<p>Service 9: GIS-Based Solution for Sustainable Heritage Maintenance</p>	<p>Data quality issues: Inaccuracies were identified in the baseline input data. Information on past renovation works proved particularly difficult to reconstruct and validate in practice, due to incomplete and inconsistent historical records. The service provider is currently developing a corrective tool to address and improve data consistency.</p>

2.4. Pilot 4 - Riga, Latvia

2.4.1. Services Implemented During Full Operation Phase

Table 7 Services to be Implemented in Pilot 4 and their implementation status

Services to be implemented in Pilot 4	Testing Status	Use	Users	Current Use
<p>Service 2: Modelling and simulation environment</p>	<p>Testing planned in Q1 2026</p>	<p>Ad-hoc</p>	<p>Admin users</p>	<p>The service is being prepared for the testing.</p>
<p>Service 3: Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning</p>	<p>Testing started in Q1 2026</p>	<p>Ad-hoc</p>	<p>Admin users</p>	<p>The service is being prepared for testing and use in early 2026. It has been demonstrated to the pilot and now testing with the stakeholders will follow.</p>
<p>Service 4: Indoor environmental quality and</p>	<p>Testing started in Q3 2025</p>	<p>Continuous</p>	<p>Admin users</p>	<p>RPR has tested service and demonstrated it to RPR's project stakeholders. The service ensures continuous monitoring IEQ parameters in the pilot building. The service supports periodic operational</p>

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comfort optimisation				adjustments aimed at improving thermal comfort and overall indoor conditions during daily operation.
Service 9: GIS-Based Solution for Sustainable Heritage Maintenance	Testing started in Q3 2025	Ad-hoc	Admin users	RPR have seen the test version of the service and the testing started in mid-March.

2.4.2. Progress During Full Operation Phase

During the full deployment phase, Pilot 4 progressed across four services at different levels of maturity.

For **Service 2 (Modelling and Simulation Environment)**, the service remains under development, with user sessions and testing activities planned for Q1 2026 as part of the structured deployment schedule.

Service 3 (Decision Support Tool for Optimal Renovation Planning) advanced through user sessions and testing activities conducted in January 2026. Further demonstration and testing involving stakeholders were done in February 2026.

Service 4 (Indoor Environmental Quality and Comfort Optimisation) progressed through configuration and parameter adjustment, followed by testing sessions under real operational conditions. Continuous data collection was established, supported by user onboarding for administrative users and ongoing operational coordination with the service provider. Additional demonstration and stakeholder testing activities were done in 2026.

Finally, **Service 9 (GIS-Based Solution for Sustainable Heritage Maintenance)** underwent configuration and parameter adjustment, testing sessions, and the integration of additional pilot-specific data. User onboarding and coordination with the service provider were carried out, with demonstration to stakeholder in February 2026, and testing started in mid-March 2026

2.4.3. Observed Challenges During Operation

Table 8 Challenges identified during service operation by Pilot 4

Services to be implemented in Pilot 4	Challenges Observed
Service 2: Modelling and simulation environment	No operational challenges identified.
Service 3: Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	The initial service testing phase revealed no operational challenges. The next testing phase was conducted to validate the service from different perspectives, addressing the needs of various stakeholders.
Service 4: Indoor environmental quality and comfort optimisation	The indoor air quality sensor was installed without any delay. However, due to internal bureaucratic processes, the installation of the sound and light sensors took longer than planned. Once the sensors were installed, data was collected smoothly, except for occasional instances when sensors required battery replacement and the data flow had to be restored.

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Service 9: GIS-Based Solution for Sustainable Heritage Maintenance

Data quality issues: The open database of all cultural heritage buildings in Latvia was used as the baseline input data for the pilot. However, it must be pointed out, that taking into account the data specifications, it was challenging to gather data for the service specific.

2.5. Gdynia, Poland

2.5.1. Services Implemented During Full Operation Phase

Table 9 Services to be Implemented in Pilot 5 and their implementation status

Services to be implemented in Pilot 5	Testing Status	Use	Users	Current Use
Service 0: Smartification & Data Exchange Platform	Testing started in Q1 2026	Ad-hoc	Admin users	The service is being prepared for testing and use in early 2026. It is intended to inform the building owner about the building performance together with data analysis.
Service 1: Interactive screen use and AR VR interfaces for heritage building design and renovation construction	Testing started in Q4 2025	Continuous	Admin users, building owner and managers, occupants	The service is under testing. At this moment the service enables with AR glasses to visualize the building defects on a 3D model and illustrates the sequence of actions required for the renovation façade. The service supports the maintenance process. Next step is to visualize the renovation scenario for the pilot.
Service 3: Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	Testing started in Q1 2026	Ad-hoc	Admin users	The service is being prepared for testing and use in early 2026. It is intended to compare alternative renovation scenarios and support medium- to long-term strategic decision-making related to building upgrades.
Service 6: Digital Twin for heritage facilities' real-time monitoring and management	Testing started in Q1 2026	Ad-hoc	Admin users, building owner	<p>The Building Information Model (BIM) model and real-time monitoring data (temperature, humidity, noise, CO₂) from the Indoor Air quality sensors installed in the pilot were provided to the service developer. In addition, other static data were supplied, including information on the building's various pathologies, as well as accessibility and inclusion assessment forms.</p> <p>The tool will provide information on the building's performance, including real-time monitoring of indoor environmental quality in the monitored apartments, energy efficiency indicators, and energy-saving scenarios.</p>

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Service 8: Preventive maintenance with H-BIM	Testing started in Q1 2026	Ad-hoc	Admin users, building owner	It will also enable the geolocation of building pathologies together with detailed information about them, quantify the building's levels of accessibility and inclusion, and generate accessible routes within the building. The service is under development. The service is being prepared for testing and use in early 2026.
				The BIM model, cloud point and details about deterioration of the building were provided to the service developer. The service is under development. The service is being prepared for testing and use in early 2026.

2.5.2. Progress During Full Operation Phase

During the full deployment phase, **Pilot 5** advanced multiple services through development, testing, and iterative refinement activities.

For **Service 0 (Smartification & Data Exchange Platform)**, development activities were carried out, followed by service introduction and user onboarding. Testing sessions under real operational conditions were initiated in Q1 2026, supported by consultation and feedback exchanges with the service developer and further improvement steps where required.

Service 1 (Interactive Screen Use & AR/VR Interfaces) progressed through continued development and a first round of consultation with the service provider. Pilot-specific data, including the BIM model and cloud point, were provided to support deployment. Testing under real operational conditions has been ongoing from Q4 2025 through Q2 2026, accompanied by structured feedback and service refinement where necessary.

For **Service 3 (Decision Support Tool for Optimal Renovation Planning)**, development activities were undertaken alongside service introduction and user onboarding. Testing sessions under real operational conditions were initiated in Q1 2026, supported by consultation with the service provider and subsequent improvement actions as needed.

Service 6 (Digital Twin for Heritage Facilities' Real-Time Monitoring) advanced through development and an initial consultation round with the service provider. Real pilot data, including the BIM model and real-time monitoring parameters (temperature, humidity, noise, CO₂), were provided to support service deployment. Testing sessions began in Q1 2026, accompanied by feedback exchanges and iterative improvement steps.

Finally, **Service 8 (Preventive Maintenance with H-BIM)** progressed through development and an initial consultation phase. Pilot data, including the BIM model, cloud point, and deterioration details, were supplied to the service developer. Testing under real operational conditions commenced in Q1 2026, supported by consultation and feedback mechanisms to enable further refinement where required.

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2.5.3. Observed Challenges During Operation

Table 10 Challenges identified during service operation by Pilot 5

Services to be implemented in Pilot 5	Challenges Observed
Service 0: Smartification & Data Exchange Platform	No operational challenges identified to date, as testing sessions are scheduled to begin in Q1 2026.
Service 1: Interactive screen use and AR VR interfaces for heritage building design and renovation construction	At the beginning, operating the Augmented Reality (AR) glasses and the service requires some learning. Initially, it can be challenging to zoom in on objects or navigate the menu, but this becomes easier with practice. During testing, it was concluded that the service would also benefit from the use of Augmented Reality to present potential renovation scenarios to the cultural heritage officer, the building owner, and the occupants. This would enable the collection of feedback and facilitate agreement on the renovation scenario among all parties. For this reason, renovation scenarios were prepared in a BIM environment in accordance with the guidelines provided by the cultural heritage officer, whose approval is required for the final design. Augmented Reality can therefore serve as an effective tool for design coordination and decision-making between different stakeholders.
Service 3: Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	No operational challenges identified to date.
Service 6: Digital Twin for heritage facilities' real-time monitoring and management	No operational challenges identified to date.
Service 8: Preventive maintenance with H-BIM	No operational challenges identified to date, as testing sessions are scheduled to begin in Q1 2026.

2.6. Pilot 6 - Valladolid, Spain

2.6.1. Services Implemented During Full Operation Phase

Table 11 Services to be Implemented in Pilot 6 and their implementation status

Services to be implemented in Pilot 6	Testing Status	Use	Users	Current Use
Service 0: Smartification & Data Exchange Platform	Testing started in Q1 2026	Ad-hoc	Admin users	The service is being prepared for testing and use in early 2026.
Service 1: Interactive screen use & AR-VR interfaces	Testing started in Q1 2026	Ad-hoc	Admin users, building owner/heritage officers (regional)	The service is being prepared for testing during the full operation phase. It will be used to support the communication and validation of potential intervention/renovation options in a highly protected heritage building context, facilitating

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			government staff)	stakeholder understanding and feedback.
Service 3: Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	Testing started in Q1 2026	Ad-hoc	Admin users, building owner/decision-makers	The service is being prepared for early 2026 testing. It will support the comparison of alternative renovation scenarios and decision-making under strong regulatory and organisational constraints.
Service 6: Digital Twin for heritage facilities' real-time monitoring	Testing started in Q1 2026	Ad-hoc	Admin users, building owner	The BIM model and real-time monitoring data (temperature, humidity, noise, CO ₂) from the Indoor Air quality sensors installed in the pilot were provided to the service developer.
Service 8: Preventive maintenance H-BIM	Testing started in Q1 2026	Ad-hoc	Admin users, building owner/maintenance staff	The H-BIM model of the Monastery has been structured and enriched according to the service protocol. Initial demonstration tests have been conducted in the pilot. The service supports the inspector by guiding the inspection process, updating maintenance data linked to specific building elements, and generating an updated IFC model enriched with the latest inspection and maintenance information.

2.6.2. Progress During Full Operation Phase

During the full operation phase, activities related to **Service 0 (Smartification & Data Exchange Platform)** focused on service development and preparatory deployment steps. The service was introduced to pilot stakeholders, followed by user onboarding activities. Testing sessions are scheduled for Q1 2026 under real operational conditions. Throughout this process, continuous consultation has been maintained with the service provider, with structured feedback provided to support potential refinements. Further service improvements will be implemented where necessary based on testing outcomes.

For **Service 1 (Interactive screen use & AR-VR interfaces)**, progress has centred on service development and alignment with the specific needs of the pilot, taking into account local regulatory constraints. Pilot-specific content and data have been prepared to support upcoming testing sessions. Coordination meetings with the service provider have been conducted to define testing scenarios planned for Q1–Q2 2026. Ongoing consultation and feedback mechanisms are in place to support iterative service improvement as deployment advances.

Implementation of **Service 3 (Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning)** has included service development activities and structured introduction to pilot stakeholders. User onboarding has been initiated, and testing sessions are planned for Q1 2026. Regular consultation meetings with the service provider ensure that pilot-specific requirements are reflected in the tool's configuration. Feedback gathered during testing will inform any necessary refinements and further optimisation.

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Service 6 (Digital Twin for heritage facilities' real-time monitoring) has progressed through coordinated development with the service provider, including an initial consultation phase to clearly define the scope of deployment and avoid functional overlap with Service 8. The pilot has provided essential datasets for deployment, including the BIM model and real-time monitoring data (temperature, humidity, noise, CO₂). A second round of data collection addressed accessibility and inclusion assessment, including building-level Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and identification of priority accessible routes per floor. Testing sessions under real operational conditions are scheduled for Q1 2026. Continuous consultation and feedback exchanges are ongoing to support service refinement and optimisation where required.

For **Service 8 (Preventive maintenance H-BIM)**, development has been carried out in close coordination with the service provider. Initial consultation meetings were held to define the deployment strategy within the pilot context. A first round of data gathering was completed, including provision of the H-BIM model structured according to the defined protocol, point cloud data, construction materials, historical documentation, and identified pathologies based on the Technical Inspection methodology. Initial demonstration tests under real operational conditions are planned for Q1 2026. Feedback mechanisms are in place to support further refinement and service optimisation as needed.

2.6.3. Observed Challenges During Operation

Table 12 Challenges identified during service operation by Pilot 6

Services to be implemented in Pilot 6	Challenges Observed
Service 0: Smartification & Data Exchange Platform	No operational challenges identified to date, as testing sessions are scheduled to begin in Q1 2026.
Service 1: Interactive screen use & AR-VR interfaces	The high level of heritage protection and the architectural complexity of the Monastery significantly impacted the HBIM modelling process. No more operational challenges identified to date, as testing sessions are scheduled to begin in Q1 2026.
Service 3: Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	No operational challenges identified to date, as testing sessions are scheduled to begin in Q1 2026.
Service 6: Digital Twin for heritage facilities' real-time monitoring	The high level of heritage protection and the architectural complexity of the Monastery significantly impacted the HBIM modelling process. The installation of monitoring equipment was highly restricted due to the building's heritage protection status and its function as the regional government headquarters. Sensor deployment required extensive administrative procedures and security clearances.
Service 8: Preventive maintenance H-BIM	The high level of heritage protection and the architectural complexity of the Monastery significantly impacted the HBIM modelling process. The irregular geometries, historical stratification, and detailed constructive features required a higher level of modelling precision and semantic structuring, which extended the development timeline beyond initial expectations. In addition, access restrictions and strict security protocols associated with the building's administrative use limited data capture activities and required additional coordination and bureaucratic procedures during inspection and model validation phases.

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2.7. Pilot 7 - Visby, Sweden

2.7.1. Services Implemented During Full Operation Phase

Table 13 Services to be Implemented in Pilot 7 and their implementation status

Services to be implemented in Pilot 7	Testing Status	Use	Users	Current Use
Service 0: Smartification & Data Exchange Platform	Testing started in Q1 2026	Ad-hoc	Building managers	Data visualization is under development.
s.2: Modelling & simulation environment	Not Started	Ad hoc	End users, Building managers	The service is being prepared. It will be used to inform decisions on energy efficiency measures for one section of the Kulturum building.
Service 3: Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	Not Started	Ad-hoc	Policy makers, local decision-makers	The service will be implemented in June 2026 for the whole building stock in Visby.
Service 5: Energy forecasting and data-driven intelligent management	Not Started	Ad-hoc	Building managers	The service will be used to enhance smart control of heating.
Service 9: GIS-Based Solution for Sustainable Heritage Maintenance: Supports long-term maintenance planning and resource management	Testing started in Q1 2026	Ad-hoc	Policy makers, local decision-makers	The service was presented in February and there is now further data collection and validation.
Service 10: Heritage building environmental climate scenarios	Testing started in Q1 2026	Ad-hoc	Policy makers, local decision-makers	A demo was shown in February and development is now being made independently by the service provider.

2.7.2. Progress During Full Operation Phase

During the full deployment phase, **Pilot 7** focused primarily on preparatory activities, data provision, and coordination with service providers across the planned services.

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For **Service 0 (Smartification & Data Exchange Platform)**, development efforts concentrated on data visualisation improvements, alongside maintenance of installed sensors following changes to Wi-Fi network Service Set Identifiers (SSIDs).

Regarding **Service 2 (Modelling and Simulation Environment)**, relevant pilot data were transmitted to the service provider, and the pilot is currently awaiting feedback to proceed with further implementation steps.

For **Service 3 (Decision Support Tool for Optimal Renovation Planning)**, a dedicated researcher was recruited to advance building stock modelling activities, within which the service will be integrated. While final modelling results are expected by the end of June, implementation is planned to continue progressively throughout the spring.

Service 5 (Energy Forecasting and Intelligent Management) remains at an early stage, with progress currently constrained by technical challenges described in the subsequent subsection.

For **Service 9 (GIS-Based Solution for Sustainable Heritage Maintenance)**, dialogue with the service provider focused on identifying additional data needs related to renovation records and data validation. A potential data sharing between the building stock model developed in service 3 and service 9 is currently being investigated.

A prototype of Service 10 (Heritage Buildings Environmental Climate Scenarios) was Applied to Visby was demonstrated for local decision-makers in February. The final version is being developed and there is currently no need of more input from the pilot.

2.7.3. Observed Challenges During Operation

Table 14 Challenges identified during service operation by Pilot 7

Services to be implemented in Pilot 7	Challenges Observed
Service 0: Smartification & Data Exchange Platform	The data in the cloud have to be made interpretable for building managers. There has been a lot of work to re-establish connection after change of WIFI. The thick walls make Bluetooth (e.g., motion sensors) and WIFI connection more difficult. The users do not want the sensors to be visible and move them, sometimes turning them off. Access to the rooms depends on individuals. See also s.5.
s.2: Modelling & simulation environment	Data was sent to service providers and we wait for feedback. The web interface of the service was not fit for purpose (a complex building).
Service 3: Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	No operational challenges identified to date, as the service has not started yet.
Service 5: Energy forecasting and data-driven intelligent management	There has been delay regarding access to consumption data for district heating, essential for the service. The delay was due to unforeseen renovation activities in the building. Now we have access to the data but still have to solve the export of live data to the service provider.
Service 9: GIS-Based Solution for Sustainable Heritage Maintenance: Supports long-term maintenance planning and resource management	The service is already available and the UI works well. There is a need to add information to the database to increase usability.

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Service 10: Heritage building environmental climate scenarios

The service has been demonstrated by the service providers, and development is carried out without need for any pilot data at this stage.

2.8. Pilot 8 - İzmir, Turkey

2.8.1. Services Implemented During Full Operation Phase

Table 15 Services to be Implemented in Pilot 8 and their implementation status

Services to be implemented in Pilot 8	Testing Status	Use	Users	Current Use
Service 0: Smartification & Data Exchange Platform	Not Started	Ad-hoc	Admin Users	The service is being prepared for testing and use by March 2026.
s.2: Modelling & simulation environment	Not Started	Ad-hoc	End Users	Service under development.
Service 3: Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	Not started	Ad-hoc	End Users	Service under development.
s.7: Real-time insights on activity and mobility patterns	Not Started	Continuous	Admin users	Delays in sensor installation. Training expected to begin after March 2026.
Service 10: Heritage building environmental climate scenarios	Not Started.	Ad-hoc (pending service provider confirmation)	Admin users	Further communication with the service providers is required to define data range. Service under development.

2.8.2. Progress During Full Operation Phase

During the full deployment phase, **Pilot 8** focused primarily on preparatory technical setup, data provision, and coordination with service providers across the planned replication services.

For **Service 0 (Smartification & Data Exchange Platform)**, installation of IEQ Netatmo, BLU-Motion, and BLU-Door/Window sensors was completed in January 2025, and data transfer was initiated. However, interruptions in the Wi-Fi connection have affected the proper functioning of some devices. The service remains under construction.

Service 2 (Modelling & simulation environment), **Service 3 (Decision Support Tool for Optimal Renovation Planning)** and **Service 7 (Real-Time Insights on Activity and Mobility Patterns)** are currently under construction, with further implementation steps pending completion of technical prerequisites and coordination processes.

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Regarding **Service 10 (Heritage Buildings Environmental Climate Scenarios)**, raw climate data for Izmir (1971–2000 averages of temperature and precipitation), together with future projections for 2024–2040, 2041–2070, and 2071–2098, were shared with CARTIF in November 2025. These datasets, prepared by the General Directorate of Meteorology for a previous study of the Izmir Historic Port City Area, were provided alongside an English translation of the corresponding guidance documentation to support service development.

2.8.3. Observed Challenges During Operation

Table 16 Challenges identified during service operation by Pilot 8

Services to be implemented in Pilot 8	Challenges Observed
Service 0: Smartification & Data Exchange Platform	Due to the thick walls and size of the historical building, the Wi-Fi system has proven inadequate, especially since the IEQ Netatmo sensors require a strong Wi-Fi connection, resulting in unreliable data reception. The procurement process, scheduled to begin in February/March, will initially focus on strengthening the Wi-Fi network and ensuring the existing sensors function properly; the second phase involves installing people counting and a few more Netatmo devices arriving from abroad. The pilot expects to achieve clearer data reception after receiving the Wi-Fi network boosting service.
s.2: Modelling & simulation environment	No operational challenges identified to date.
Service 3: Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	No operational challenges identified to date.
s.7: Real-time insights on activity and mobility patterns	Jan 2026: The pilot informed REGEA about the expected timeline for the installation of sensors for s.7. The pilot is currently coordinating with the IT Department for the procurement phase, which takes some time due to the municipality's strict procedures. The technical specifications are ready and will be submitted after the mayor's approval. The pilot aims to complete the sensor procurement and installation by March at the latest, possibly earlier depending on stock availability and delivery times.
Service 10: Heritage building environmental climate scenarios	Providing a city-wide data set is not easy since the city of Izmir has a fairly large surface area, approximately 12,000 km ² . If the service provider can limit the minimum required application area for this service, then we may correspond with the relevant units in the municipality to obtain data (Buildings' geometry and geolocation, & Digital Elevation Model) for a specific area that includes our pilot building. Pilot aims to increase communication on this matter and be on the same track.

3. Stakeholder Collaboration – Full Deployment Phase Activities & Outcomes

3.1. Overview of Stakeholder Engagement in the Full Deployment Phase

In the full deployment phase, stakeholder engagement moved from conceptual planning to structured implementation and iterative refinement of INHERIT services. While D5.2 established the stakeholder architecture, defined priority groups and outlined prospective formats, this section demonstrates how these structures were operationalised in practice.

The stakeholder engagement approach of INHERIT is built around the Multi-Layer Stakeholder Architecture, which functioned as a stable engagement backbone. Implemented workshops and engagement activities are therefore presented in a structured manner, distinguishing between retrospective and prospective actions and specifying their dates, formats and stakeholder groups involved.

Building on the stakeholder categories defined in D5.2 and the co-creation principles outlined in D2.1 “*Social Labs Methodological Handbook, high-level requirements*”, the architecture structured participation across three interconnected levels: **(1) User level** (end-users and potential end-users), **(2) Organisational level** (admin users), and **(3) Systemic level** (quadruple helix stakeholders). In the deployment phase, this architecture served not only as a mapping framework but also as a coordination instrument, clarifying roles, aligning engagement intensity with implementation needs, and ensuring that stakeholder inputs were effectively channelled into service development, governance alignment and social impact assessment.

Workshop and stakeholder engagement activities are structured into retrospective and prospective dimensions. Implementation was carried out through **Social Labs Vol. 2 and Vol. 3**, the second **INHERIT Multi-Stakeholder Forum (MSF)**, the updated second round of the **Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA)**, and targeted co-creation workshops on user scenarios, S-LCA indicators and key user personas. Engagement activities focused on testing and adapting INHERIT tools and services in real pilot contexts, clarifying user roles across the three stakeholder levels, and collecting structured evidence on social, environmental and organisational impacts. The deployment phase therefore centred on translating co-creation principles into practice: refining service functionalities based on stakeholder feedback, aligning technical solutions with governance and policy requirements, and embedding New European Bauhaus (NEB) values and ISO 26000 principles into operational decision-making.

3.2. Stakeholder Engagement Actions Implemented

3.2.1. Stakeholder Architecture and Stakeholder Groups Engaged During Deployment

During the full deployment phase, the INHERIT stakeholder architecture structured stakeholder engagement across all project activities. It built upon the stakeholder categories defined in D5.2 and the co-creation principles outlined in D2.1, ensuring their consistent application throughout implementation. The resulting Multi-Layer Stakeholder Architecture provides a stable, coordinated framework that defined roles and coordinated interaction formats, and levels of participation across the project activities (**Figure 1**).

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Figure 1 Multi-layer INHERIT stakeholder architecture

The architecture structured stakeholder engagement across each pilot and within the Multi-Stakeholder Forum (MSF) by applying the project's stakeholder mapping and categorisation logic. It organised participation across key defined stakeholder groups: (a) *end-users and potential end-users*; (b) *admin users, defined as Owners, Operators, and Decision-makers (OODs)*; and (c) *quadruple helix stakeholders representing civil society, education and research, policymaking, and cultural and creative sectors*. Through differentiated engagement levels and participation formats, the architecture ensured role clarity, iterative feedback loops, and alignment between user-centred co-creation processes, operational governance requirements, and broader systemic perspectives.

Activities conducted through the Social Labs (SL), the S-LCA, and the MSF engaged actors across all three levels of the architecture, linking user-centred design, operational feasibility, and systemic sustainability. Stakeholder mapping remained an iterative process throughout the deployment phase, with the stakeholder pool regularly updated to reflect evolving roles, interests, and influence. Engagement approaches were continuously refined based on feedback generated across these formats, ensuring responsiveness and adaptive coordination.

At the **User level**, services are co-designed and iteratively refined through the active involvement of end-users and potential end-users in SLs, user scenario workshops, and MSF workshops. Their needs, expectations, and contextual experiences directly inform service development, ensuring relevance and responsiveness.

At the **Organisational level**, admin users participate in co-design and co-creation, aligning technical developments, policy requirements and managerial strategies with NEB² and International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO) 26000:100³ principles. Through the S-LCA, they are grouped as OODs, bringing governance, regulatory and managerial perspectives into the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) S-LCA⁴ approach under the "Promoting Social Responsibility" category and related ISO 26000 guidance. Their involvement helps assess how INHERIT services

² https://new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/index_en

³ https://iso26000.info/wp-content/uploads/2017/06/ISO-26000_2010_E_OBPpages.pdf

⁴ <https://www.unep.org/resources/report/guidelines-social-life-cycle-assessment-products>

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implement and demonstrate robust organisational governance, environmental responsibility and responsible community engagement.

At the **Systemic level**, core stakeholders from the Quadruple Helix sectors⁵, representing civil society, education and research, policymaking, and cultural and creative industries are mobilised through participation in SLs, S-LCA surveys, and MSF activities. Their contribution broadens societal representation, strengthens policy alignment, and embeds diverse expertise into the co-creation process.

Taken together, these three interconnected levels form a coherent stakeholder engagement ecosystem that systematically links user needs, operational realities and broader governance considerations. This multi-layered approach supports service development while creating the conditions for the long-term sustainability of cultural heritage management outcomes. Building on this conceptual and structural framework, the following section showcases the concrete stakeholder engagement measures implemented during the development period, outlining the workshops and engagement activities carried out across pilots and MSF.

3.2.2. Implemented Workshops and Engagement Activities

Implemented workshops and engagement activities are structured into retrospective and prospective activities, including the dates, formats and stakeholders involved.

3.2.2.1. Workshops and engagement formats implemented

Based on the engagement approach described in D5.2, a number of workshops and networking activities were carried out during the deployment phase, involving end-users, admin users and core stakeholders from different sectors.

During the deployment period, **Social Labs Vol. 2 and Vol. 3 (SL2 and SL3)** were organised in pilots, creating a continuous engagement process that moves from initial stakeholder mapping and needs analysis to testing prototypes, co-designing interventions and refining solutions in real-world settings. Social Labs in INHERIT function as collaborative spaces for stakeholder engagement, bringing together actors from research and innovation, cultural heritage practice, local and regional authorities, energy agencies, the private sector and civil society to address the complex challenges of decarbonising and renovating historic buildings while preserving their heritage value and integrating NEB values.

Social Labs Vol. 2 (SL2) workshops, implemented between M14-16, focused in particular on strengthening collaboration with pilot partners and deepening engagement around INHERIT services, digital tools and assessment frameworks, including a capacity-building module on co-creation in each workshop to equip participants with methods and skills for collaborative problem-solving. Across the pilots, stakeholders met in various formats (conference side-events, pilot-site meetings and public fairs) to discuss how to combine energy efficiency, accessibility and resilience with heritage conservation, identify barriers such as financial constraints, regulatory complexity, limited technical capacity and difficulties in involving residents, and explore enabling factors such as public-private partnerships, EU and national green financing, smart monitoring and decision-support tools, H-BIM and DT, as well as awareness-raising activities, educational programmes and participatory workshops. Across the seven pilots implementing SL2, **a total of 220 stakeholders participated**. Engagement levels varied across pilots, ranging from 13 participants in the Latvian pilot (RPR) to 46 participants in both the Spanish (CARTIF) and Croatian (REGEA) pilots,

⁵<https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5e4d98f00&appId=PPGMS>

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reflecting the different stakeholder ecosystems and local engagement strategies. The Spanish pilot (CARTIF) engaged 46 stakeholders, including representatives from the science and research sector (architects, engineers, and physicists), heritage managers, conservators and restorers, as well as actors from the public sector working in heritage, culture and tourism, together with R&D stakeholders. The Greek pilot (ELLET) involved 44 participants, primarily representatives from public authorities such as the Ministry of Culture, the Ministry of Energy and the Municipality of Athens, as well as architects from the private sector and representatives from academia. The Polish pilot (FASADA) engaged 18 stakeholders, mainly officials from the Gdynia City Hall and representatives of private construction companies. Participants included staff from the Department of Energy, the City Visual Artist's Office and the Municipal Heritage Conservator's Office, including specialists, inspectors and managers. A key stakeholder group responsible for defining renovation guidelines for the cultural heritage building was successfully engaged.

The Turkish pilot (IBB) involved 39 stakeholders representing a mix of public authorities and policy makers (e.g., culture and tourism departments, libraries, city archives and heritage promotion units), the private sector (including a development agency), higher education institutions and NGOs working on materials, climate and sustainable development. Approximately 87% of participants represented public authorities, while 13% came from the private and civil society sectors. The Croatian pilot (REGEA) engaged 46 participants representing public authorities, policymakers, academia, conservation experts, private sector actors and media representatives. The participants were primarily professionals aged between 30 and 60, with a balanced gender representation. The Latvian pilot (RPR) involved 13 stakeholders, representing organisations working in the fields of energy efficiency, building renovation, building management policies and financial planning for building management, including investments and energy efficiency improvements in cultural heritage buildings. Finally, the Swedish pilot (UU) engaged 14 stakeholders, including representatives from the municipality, the national heritage authority, the university sector and one private sector actor from the architectural field. Each SL2 event concluded with the definition of next steps in the form of Lab Projects, ranging from energy audits and technical assessments to urban-space improvements, accessibility measures, student collaborations and targeted outreach actions, thereby creating concrete pathways for testing INHERIT services in real contexts and strengthening long-term stakeholder collaboration around sustainable, inclusive cultural heritage renovation.

These activities were followed by **Social Labs Vol.3 (SL3) events** (implemented in M23-27), which continued the dialogue with stakeholders and supported more in-depth feedback and reflection at pilot level. The third round of Social Lab workshops (SL3) further broadened and deepened stakeholder engagement in INHERIT and is still ongoing, but first results already show clear trends. SL3 events brought together an even more diverse mix of actors than before, adding new groups such as tourism, technology and accessibility experts, local activists and user representatives to the existing networks of heritage professionals and public authorities. Across the six pilots that have already implemented SL3 events, **a total of 128 stakeholders participated**. Engagement levels varied across pilots, ranging from 9 stakeholders in the Latvian pilot to 32 stakeholders in the Turkish pilot, reflecting the specific context and stakeholder ecosystem of each site. The Croatian pilot (REGEA) engaged 17 participants, mainly cultural heritage site managers, public authorities, technology providers, researchers and other stakeholders involved in heritage management and digital service development. The Polish pilot (FASADA) involved 24 stakeholders, including local residents, cultural heritage interpreters, NGO representatives, university experts and municipal representatives. The Swedish pilot (UU) engaged 28 participants, mainly students, researchers, local

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residents and stakeholders interested in the sustainable management of heritage buildings. The Greek pilot (ELLET) brought together 18 participants, including students, young professionals, citizens and experts working on heritage accessibility and inclusion. The Latvian pilot (RPR) involved 9 representatives, primarily from national cultural heritage authorities, regional planning bodies and municipal departments. Finally, the Turkish pilot (IBB) engaged 32 stakeholders, including representatives of cultural heritage authorities, municipal departments, researchers and technology actors. Overall, the composition of participants illustrates the multi-actor and cross-sectoral character of stakeholder engagement in INHERIT, combining heritage professionals, public authorities, researchers, civil society actors and local community members. This diversity reflects the project's objective to integrate technical innovation with social inclusion and community participation in the sustainable management of cultural heritage sites. Due to limitations in the pilot implementation timeline and adjustments in the pilot configuration, the French pilot (BOUYGUES) will implement a merged SL2–SL3 workshop planned for M31. This approach allows the pilot to consolidate the engagement process and ensure that stakeholders can meaningfully contribute to the further development and validation of the INHERIT services within the updated pilot context. In the Spanish pilot (CARTIF), Social Lab Vol.3 has been postponed pending further development of Service 8, in order to ensure that stakeholder engagement can take place on the basis of a sufficiently mature service concept and therefore generate meaningful and targeted feedback. The results and outcomes of this workshop will be reported in the next relevant project deliverables, once the activity has been implemented. Across the pilots, the workshops focused on social accessibility, inclusive use and visitor experience in heritage buildings and areas, using interactive formats (walks, roleplay, open stakeholder corners, onsite discussions) to explore how different user groups perceive and use cultural heritage spaces. Participants identified typical physical, informational and organisational barriers that limit access for people with disabilities, elderly citizens, families and visitors, and cocreated ideas for low-cost, reversible physical adjustments, digital tools and multifunctional “community hub” uses. The first outcomes underline that accessibility is not only a technical issue but a social value, and that INHERIT solutions are most impactful when they combine heritage preservation, sustainable renovation and active community participation.

The 2nd INHERIT MSF event was organised by ZSI in M21. The event explored how to boost energy efficiency in cultural heritage buildings through the lens of the NEB. It served as a collaborative platform for mutual learning and networking, bringing together scientists, cultural and creative industry professionals, policy actors and cultural heritage users (**Figure 2**). The MSF brought together an EU-level stakeholder community with 41 participants, including architects, researchers, experts, construction professionals and other cultural heritage actors to discuss how energy efficiency in heritage buildings can be advanced through innovation, retrofit strategies and the values of the NEB, with a notable share of participants joining the Forum series for the first time and expressing strong interest in integrating NEB principles into their work. An interactive poll at the outset mapped participants' backgrounds, prior Forum participation and familiarity with NEB projects, helping to tailor the discussions and confirming both the diversity and high engagement potential of the audience. The programme addressed topics such as climate-resilient and accessible retrofitting, green technologies and the social dimensions of energy-efficient design and included NEB Excellence contributions on earthen construction and NEB-aligned timber and bio-based innovations, which illustrated how sustainability, aesthetics and inclusion can be combined in practice. Through presentations, Questions and Answers (Q&A) and moderated exchanges, the Forum supported mutual learning, cross-sector collaboration and the translation of NEB values into

D5.3- INHERIT pilots' execution documentation –full pilot operation phase practical and policy-relevant approaches for adaptive reuse and energy performance in cultural heritage buildings. The presented updated S-LCA framework also supported a deeper stakeholder understanding of the methodology, clarified perceived risks and priorities, and fed directly into the refinement of INHERIT services and the design of the social impact assessment.

Figure 2 2nd INHERIT Multi-Stakeholder Forum (MSF) event

Furthermore, the first phase of the **co-creation of the INHERIT solutions** (M4–M12) focused on collecting information and feedback on the INHERIT services from project stakeholders and end users, as well as identifying the needs of the different pilots to support the effective integration of the services into site-specific CH buildings. During this phase, a series of meetings with pilots and service providers was conducted. Based on these interactions, a user story template (to collect user scenarios) and a service description template (to document service characteristics) were developed. The application of these templates resulted in the collection of 28 user stories, along with their corresponding service descriptions, providing a structured overview of user needs and service functionalities.

To further support the collection of user requirements, **Co-creating the INHERIT solutions and user scenarios Workshop** was implemented by SLG within the framework of Task 2.4. in M8, involving representatives from all eight INHERIT pilots and end users from sectors relevant to CH. The workshop was implemented in close coordination with the pilot partners and provided input that also informed WP5 activities related to service deployment preparation and alignment of functionalities with pilot needs. The workshop was attended by 44 participants from different European countries, with a balanced gender distribution (56% female, 44% male). Participants included researchers, application developers, engineers, architects, and other professionals. Through collaborative brainstorming activities, participants provided valuable feedback on user requirements, addressing not only the strengths and opportunities of the proposed services, but also identifying potential weaknesses, threats, and barriers to implementation. The insights gathered during this phase will contribute to the consolidation of the final user requirements, supporting the effective development and integration of INHERIT services across the pilot sites.

Stakeholder meetings conducted across the pilot sites provided valuable insights into the challenges, recommendations and lessons learned related to the implementation of INHERIT solutions. Across all pilots, stakeholders consistently highlighted the need for improved accessibility, both physical and digital, as well as the importance of user-centred and inclusive approaches. Common barriers identified include physical constraints in heritage buildings, regulatory limitations, insufficient funding, and limited stakeholder engagement.

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In the Croatian pilot (REGEA), stakeholders recommended the introduction of digital accessibility tools, low-cost and reversible adaptations, and stronger involvement of vulnerable groups. Key challenges included physical barriers, lack of inclusive information, and limited community engagement. The main lesson learned is that accessibility requires a combined technical and social approach, supported by early stakeholder involvement.

In the Greek pilot (ELLET), recommendations focused on improving physical accessibility (e.g., ramps, paving), introducing digital tools, and applying reversible solutions in heritage sites. Stakeholders highlighted physical barriers, poor signage, safety issues, and the impact of over tourism on accessibility. The main lesson learned is that inclusive heritage requires multidisciplinary cooperation and user-centred design.

In the Latvian pilot (RPR), stakeholders recommended strengthening stakeholder engagement and enabling practical testing of services with end users. Identified challenges included the need for clearer financing mechanisms and long-term planning, as well as limited engagement due to funding uncertainty. The main lesson learned is that data-driven assessments support decision-making, but early alignment on funding and stakeholder involvement is critical.

In the Polish pilot (FASADA), stakeholders recommended increasing funding flexibility, strengthening community co-creation, and using digital tools (e.g., VR) for engagement. Key constraints include financial limitations and strict conservation requirements, which limit renovation feasibility. The discussions showed that strong community interest supports participatory approaches, but funding remains a key barrier.

In the Swedish pilot (UU), recommendations included reducing car use, improving public awareness, strengthening circular practices, and enhancing stakeholder engagement. Stakeholders highlighted conflicts between tourism, housing and heritage protection, as well as complex regulations and limited public understanding. The main lesson learned is that sustainable heritage management requires behavioural change, clearer governance, and stronger community involvement.

In the Turkish pilot (IBB), stakeholders recommended improving accessibility and visitor experience, introducing interactive tools (e.g., AR/VR), and defining clearer user profiles and use scenarios. Key challenges include balancing heritage preservation with increasing tourism pressure and diversifying building use for different user groups. The main lesson learned is that early stakeholder involvement and clearer definition of user needs are essential for developing sustainable and user-oriented solutions.

3.2.2.2. Perspective workshops and engagement formats planned

Building on the experience gained through the activities implemented so far, further workshops and engagement formats are planned for the coming project phases. Detailed overview of the foreseen events could be found in Table 17.

Table 17 Overview of MSF Events and Stakeholder Engagement Activities

Event/Activity	Target Audience	Objectives	Key Topics	Format
MSF Webinar Series	Heritage managers, operators, tech providers, local authorities, policymakers, researchers, students	Foster collaborative learning, link MSF with pilots, and co-develop NEB-aligned strategies for CH renovation	Smart planning and management; digital and retrofit solutions for energy efficiency; NEB-led tools for beautiful, sustainable, inclusive CH	Three online webinars

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NEB Satellite Event	MSF members, heritage professionals, CH students, educators and researchers	Showcase INHERIT tools, explore NEB-aligned approaches	Adaptive management, digital forecasting, sustainable heritage, low-impact retrofitting	Online, interactive
Online Survey on Usability	MSF members, potential end-users	Gather feedback on usability, assess effectiveness of INHERIT tools	Usability challenges, user feedback, tool refinement	Online survey
On-Demand Tailored Stakeholder Sessions	Pilot partners, stakeholders	Address site-specific challenges, co-creation strategies	CH preservation, technical and social aspects, stakeholder needs	Micro-events, workshops
Final MSF Event	All MSF stakeholders, broader public	Highlight legacy of MSF, showcase INHERIT results	Decision-support tools, capacity-building, policy briefs	Presentations, discussions

This includes the **3rd INHERIT MSF workshop series on “Sustainable and Future-Proof Cultural Heritage Buildings”**, planned for 2026 and to be organised together by ZSI and ICLEI. The series will bring together stakeholders from civil society, education and policymaking and will address the thematic priorities outlined in D5.2, while further integrating NEB principles at the level of project implementation. The three webinars, held between M30 and M33 one per month introduce the project’s e-learning packages and focus on: (1) **smart planning and management for cultural heritage buildings, including inspection protocols, multi-dimensional assessment frameworks and tools for assessing intervention feasibility and acceptability**; (2) **technical competences for next-generation solutions, presenting digital forecasting tools, smart monitoring and reversible, low-impact retrofit approaches that enhance energy performance while respecting heritage values**; and (3) **NEB-led research and tools for cultural heritage management, showcasing how INHERIT and sister projects apply NEB principles of sustainability, beauty and inclusion through methods such as interactive Reflection Circles**. The series targets heritage managers and operators, technology providers and users, local authorities and policy enablers, as well as researchers, students and educational actors, and thus engages a wide range of stakeholders who can further apply, disseminate and co-develop INHERIT results within and beyond the MSF framework. The 3rd webinar will be implemented in the form of the 3rd MSF Event during the **NEB Festival Satellite Event “Creating a New Contemporary: NEB-led Research and Tools for Management in Cultural Heritage”** is planned for June 12th, 2026, as part of the New European Bauhaus Festival, within the framework of the INHERIT MSF and the application of INHERIT is already accepted. This event will showcase innovative tools and methods for cultural heritage retrofitting, focusing on the integration of social, aesthetic, and technological aspects, and engaging INHERIT MSF members, stakeholders and practitioners from partner networks, students, as well as researchers, innovators, and organisations involved in heritage, sustainability, and social innovation to explore NEB-aligned approaches in cultural heritage management. Building on the INHERIT project’s transdisciplinary approach, the event will highlight NEB-aligned strategies that support sustainable heritage management, including adaptive management, digital forecasting tools, and low-impact retrofit techniques. It will foster collaborative learning and cross-sector dialogue, presenting INHERIT’s decision-support tools and encouraging reflection on how these approaches balance heritage

D5.3- INHERIT pilots' execution documentation –full pilot operation phase preservation with environmental sustainability. As part of the MSF format, the event will strengthen stakeholder connections, continue knowledge exchange, and ensure the long-term impact of the INHERIT project across sectors.

As part of the ongoing engagement efforts within the MSF, an **Online Survey Component on Usability** as a part of the S-LCA Survey approach, will be implemented in 2026 to gather feedback on usability from both MSF members and potential end-users of INHERIT solutions. This survey will focus on identifying key usability challenges and assessing the effectiveness of the INHERIT decision-support tools and other technological solutions. By involving MSF participants, including heritage professionals, policymakers, and researchers, as well as potential end-users from the pilot regions, the survey aims to collect valuable insights that will inform the refinement of services and ensure they meet the practical needs of users. The survey will also help in fine-tuning user scenarios and validating the tools in real-world contexts, aligning with NEB principles to ensure inclusive, sustainable, and technologically sound heritage management practices. This process will contribute to the ongoing iteration and improvement of INHERIT's tools, fostering continuous user feedback and stakeholder collaboration. Additionally, upon the pilots' request, ZSI could organise On-Demand Tailored Stakeholder Sessions for Pilot Partners. These micro-events could be specifically designed to address the challenges of each site, focusing on co-creation strategies, CH preservation, and both technical and social aspects, and would be tailored to meet the diverse needs of end-users, admin users, and core stakeholders.

A final **4th INHERIT MSF event** is foreseen for M38-M40, with the aim of highlighting the legacy of the MSF and key INHERIT project results. This includes the presentation of the INHERIT decision-support services platform, capacity-building tools, and policy briefs, as well as contributions from NEB experts. The event will build on the MSF 1-3 results and will support project exploitation activities and help maintain stakeholder connections beyond the project duration.

3.2.3. Complementary Engagement Actions Beyond the MSF

To complement the work of the MSF and sustain collaboration and learning across pilots during the deployment phase, additional stakeholder engagement actions were implemented. These activities focused on refining the internal stakeholder architecture of INHERIT, clarifying user roles and responsibilities, and translating high-level engagement objectives into more concrete co-production steps at pilot level. In addition to dedicated workshops on stakeholder roles (e.g., OODs) and key user personas for INHERIT services, partners continued to update and expand stakeholder mappings, including end-user groups, professional networks and educational actors in the pilot regions. Together, these processes helped to align service development with evolving stakeholder needs, ensured that new relevant actors could be brought into the project at appropriate moments and supported a gradual shift from exploratory dialogue towards implementation-oriented collaboration.

A dedicated **S-LCA 2 Co-Creation Workshop** was held in M26 to streamline stakeholder engagement in the Social Life-Cycle Assessment Survey approach in pilots and within the multi-stakeholder architecture. Led by ZSI, the workshop introduced partners to an updated S-LCA approach, used to gather empirical evidence and evaluate the positive or negative social impacts generated by pilot services after their implementation, as well as to monitor the evolution of social value creation over time, and clarified how results can inform decision-making at pilot sites. Participants reviewed the S-LCA framework based on ISO 14075:2024 and the 2020 UNEP Guidelines, discussed relevant stakeholder categories (local community, value-chain actors, society) and impact subcategories, and agreed a focused set of impact areas and indicators tailored to cultural heritage renovation. From

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the chosen set of stakeholder groups and impact categories, the focus of the workshop was set on the value-chain actors corresponding the OODs in INHERIT, who will be interviewed in the second S-LCA round on “*Promoting Social Responsibility*”, and to broader stakeholder groups to be addressed through surveys on cultural heritage, community engagement, public sustainability commitments and technology development.

During the workshop, participants reflected on the updated indicator set that will be central to the second S-LCA round and the associated interview guidance. They confirmed a core focus on Organisational Governance, specifying two mandatory indicators for all pilots: **G1 (Transparency and Social Responsibility in Decision-Making)** and **G2 (Alignment with Cultural Heritage Mission and Vision)**. In addition, partners co-designed the guidance for optional indicators under Community Involvement and Development (**C1 Contribution to Social and Cultural Added Value Creation, C2 Community Engagement**) and Environmental Responsibility (**E1 Potential Contribution to Environmental Performance, E2 Preserving Cultural Heritage for Future Generations**), that were selected upon relevance depending on each pilot's context and intervention type.

To further streamline End-User engagement, **the Key User Persona Workshop** was held online in M26. Organised by ZSI, as a focused session to identify and describe the primary user types of INHERIT technology services and other stakeholders who will interact with them in future cultural heritage buildings. Using a persona-based approach, the workshop translated diverse end-user roles (such as cultural heritage managers, energy and facility managers, and other OOD actors) into real-world, human-centred profiles that reflect their needs, motivations, pain points, and expectations. Following the activities in the initial phase, the persona-based workshop provided an updated perspective that was more strongly rooted in real-world challenges.

This helped to prioritise service features, tailor user experiences and anticipate challenges while respecting historical context and supporting accessibility, sustainability and engagement. That allowed to provide clearer guidance for service implementation and to establish a framework for future stakeholder engagement, particularly through the Multi-Stakeholder Forum and the INHERIT Info Desk.

During the workshop, participants jointly co-developed a typical end-user role across pilots, such as building and facility managers, energy experts and simulation engineers, conservation and cultural heritage officers, municipal decision-makers and administrative staff, owners and residents, as well as visitors for specific services (**Figure 3**).

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Figure 3 Typical End User Persona Roles Reflected by Pilots

Using interactive questions, participants explored main pain points and expectations, highlighting challenges such as high energy costs, lack of reliable building data, difficulty complying with heritage and energy regulations, limited access to scientific tools and the absence of integrated decision-support for comparing renovation options. In a final step, the group translated these insights into core needs for INHERIT solutions, including real-time and high-resolution monitoring data, user-friendly simulation tools, multi-criteria decision-support for renovation scenarios (cost, energy performance, heritage compatibility), quick checks for regulatory constraints, GIS-based learning from similar buildings and climate-impact assessment functions, thereby sharpening the user-centred requirements for service development and deployment.

The results of the Key User Persona Workshop allow for a two-level structuring of end users, complementing the user level of the Multi-Layer Stakeholder Architecture through a more detailed, functional and sector-based perspective. At the functional level, personas can be grouped into six categories: operational users, technical experts, governance and decision-makers, heritage stakeholders, owners and market actors, and societal end users. This reflects the different ways in which actors are involved in or affected by INHERIT services, ranging from operational use to planning and broader societal interaction.

These groups can be further clustered into three overarching sectors: public sector, business sector, and societal/education-related users, in line with the project's broader stakeholder categorisation. The public sector includes authorities and heritage stakeholders responsible for regulatory and decision-making processes. The business sector comprises technical experts, operational users and market actors involved in implementation and use. The societal and education-related group includes residents, visitors and associations, representing the broader community interacting with cultural heritage buildings.

These insights provide a structured basis for further activities within the project and support the translation of user needs into service-related requirements. In particular, they will be used to inform the preparation of early market feedback and testing sessions with potential end users, to be organised by service providers and methodologically supported by ZSI, as described in more detail in the following subsections.

In parallel with workshop activities, pilots and coordination partners maintained **ongoing stakeholder mapping** to ensure that engagement efforts captured relevant actors and adapted to evolving project needs. This iterative process included desk-research-based mapping of relevant

D5.3- INHERIT pilots' execution documentation –full pilot operation phase technology and cultural heritage networks of potential end users, and systematic updates of the INHERIT Stakeholder Database during the deployment period. End-user networks were further updated in the database, and new educational stakeholders tab was introduced with education stakeholders with CH focus identified for the further interactions for upcoming MSF activities in 2026. These continuous mapping efforts supported more targeted outreach for Social Lab activities and other stakeholder engagement activities.

3.3. Continuous Stakeholder Support Mechanisms

The implementation of **continuous support mechanisms** during the deployment phase builds on the framework defined in D5.2 and the **MSF Infodesk** outlined in D2.1. Continuous support was provided through structured question-and-answer–based exchanges, enabling stakeholders to reflect on emerging challenges, share perspectives and collectively explore solutions related to the implementation of INHERIT services (**Figure 4**).

Figure 4 Updated QH model of the Multi-Stakeholder Forum Infodesk

The MSF Infodesk functions as a space for thematic dialogue around key topics such as the NEB, innovation in cultural heritage buildings, sustainability and green renovation, and pathways for scaling up and collaboration. Discussions addressed, among others, how NEB values can move beyond a conceptual framework to become an everyday attitude in heritage management, how community participation can influence decision-making, and how technological innovation can be reconciled with preservation requirements. Further exchanges focused on barriers to sustainable renovation, including regulatory constraints, funding gaps and knowledge needs, as well as on mechanisms to scale up pilot solutions through training, cooperation across sectors and engagement with financial actors.

Overall, this Q&A-driven support approach enabled continuous knowledge exchange, supported the identification of new perspectives and needs within the stakeholder community, and ensured that

D5.3- INHERIT pilots' execution documentation –full pilot operation phase insights emerging from the MSF were fed back into ongoing project activities. The approach remains fully aligned with the collaboration and governance framework defined in D2.1.

In the current reporting period, these exchanges were further operationalised through the MSF2 event and related Infodesk activities, where 6 structured question blocks were raised and addressed during the Q&A sessions, covering both technical (e.g., construction materials, energy performance solutions) and strategic aspects (e.g., NEB integration, financing models). Following up on D5.2, this represents a further structured and thematically focused interaction, with direct expert input and documented responses. In addition, new material has been generated in the form of documented Q&A exchanges, Mentimeter-based feedback results, and presentation inputs, which have been integrated into ongoing S-LCA reflections and WP5 stakeholder engagement activities.

The Multi-Stakeholder Forum LinkedIn Group

The MSF LinkedIn group is used as a key channel to sustain continuous dialogue beyond Forum workshops and events. With 42 members from the MSF expert community (increasing from 32 members in the previous reporting period), it supports the exchange of questions, reflections on NEB principles, innovation and sustainability, and updates on project-related topics. Through 28 posts (including 20 new posts since the last reporting period) featuring regular news, best practices and insights on heritage management, New European Bauhaus initiatives and inclusive community practices, the group helps maintain engagement, stimulate discussion and connect stakeholders across disciplines and regions throughout the deployment phase. From Month 26 onwards, this online series is increasingly used to introduce INHERIT activities during the pilot implementation phase and to invite interested experts to upcoming MSF workshops and other engagement opportunities.

3.4. User Scenarios and Next Steps towards End-User Engagement

During the full deployment phase, stakeholder engagement activities under WP5 support the configuration, testing and validation of INHERIT services across the eight pilot sites operating as living laboratories. These activities benefit from a strong link with the co-creation processes carried out under WP2, where user stories, requirements and stakeholder feedback were collected to inform the development of the services.

Building on these insights, WP5 activities focus on aligning service implementation with the operational needs of pilots and end-users. User scenarios developed in earlier phases help clarify expected use cases, user interactions and potential value of the services, supporting the preparation of pilot testing activities.

Based on the results of the end-user persona workshops and stakeholder mapping activities, a structured basis has been established for translating user needs into service-related requirements. These insights inform the organisation of online early market feedback and testing sessions in the next period. As defined in D5.2., in line with this approach, a series of early market feedback and testing sessions will be implemented in M36–M40 as a part of the Task 5.2, covering the three main groups of potential end users, identified in end user persona workshops: public sector, business sector and societal/education-related users.

As outlined in D5.2, service providers are responsible for organising the sessions and presenting their solutions, ensuring alignment with pilot-specific use cases and technical maturity levels. ZSI will act as a knowledge broker and methodological facilitator, supporting session design, moderation, and harmonised feedback collection and documentation.

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The identification and invitation of participants is carried out jointly by service providers and pilot partners, based on stakeholder mappings, project databases and partner networks. Public sector stakeholders are primarily invited through the European Association of Historic Towns and Regions (EAHTR). Business sector stakeholders (e.g., technical experts, facility and energy managers, developers, owners) are engaged through pilot-level stakeholder networks, including contacts collected in the potential end-user database with the support of ZSI, as well as through service provider networks of the database of the dissemination and exploitation partners. Societal and education-related stakeholders (e.g., education actors, civil society organisations) are invited through ZSI educational stakeholder databases developed in T5.2 and pilot partner networks.

The sessions will be designed to collect structured feedback on usability, applicability and relevance of the services, providing input for iterative refinement during pilot implementation and supporting further decision-making within the project and dissemination, exploitation and multiplication of the services usage.

4. Full Pilot Operation & Monitoring

4.1. Overview of the Full Deployment Phase

The full pilot operation phase represents a critical transition within WP5, marking the shift from preparatory planning and framework design, as reported in D5.2, to the actual execution of INHERIT services in real-life pilot contexts. Starting from October 2025, pilot partners, service providers and WP5 coordination progressively engaged in deployment, testing and operational use activities under real operational conditions.

This phase was characterised by a high degree of heterogeneity across pilots, reflecting differences in building typologies, local governance structures, data availability, technical maturity of services and organisational readiness. As a result, services progressed at different speeds across the eight pilot sites. While several services entered testing or early operational use during the reporting period, a considerable share remained in configuration or preparatory stages due to dependencies related to data availability, infrastructure readiness and technical integration requirements. As a result, the deployment status across pilots reflects a mix of services under configuration, services entering testing phases and a smaller number already operating under real pilot conditions, highlighting the heterogeneous technical readiness of pilot environments.

Specific pilot reports presented in [Section 2](#) highlight several recurring implementation constraints affecting deployment timelines across multiple sites. These include delays in the provision of digital building models such as BIM or HBIM files, installation challenges related to sensor infrastructure and limitations in building connectivity or energy data availability. In several heritage buildings, physical characteristics such as thick masonry walls affected wireless signal transmission and required additional technical adjustments before monitoring services could operate reliably. Managing this diversity required a coordinated and adaptive approach at WP5 level.

The monitoring approach builds on the methodological framework established in Deliverable D5.2, which defined the Evaluation and Impact Assessment Framework, including the initial set of KPIs and baseline data collection for each pilot. To support harmonised reporting, a consolidated Excel-based monitoring tool was introduced, through which pilots provided updates on service status, KPI-related inputs and operational observations.

In line with the monitoring approach defined in Deliverable D5.2, deployment monitoring under Task 5.3 is organised through three iterative cycles aligned with the main phases of pilot implementation. The information presented in this chapter reflects the results of **Iteration 1**, conducted between December 2025 and the end of February 2026. During this period, structured data collection was carried out across pilots and service providers to capture the initial operational status of services during the deployment stage.

To support a structured overview of deployment progress, a consolidated cross-pilot monitoring table was introduced and used throughout the reporting period. The monitoring table was developed during the first deployment tracking iteration as a structured overview of pilot inputs and service implementation status. Based on the information provided by pilots, it evolved into a consolidated matrix summarising service status, training activities, pilot readiness to provide inputs to service providers and proposed next steps. The table also captured implementation dependencies, indicating which partner was responsible for providing missing data, equipment or development inputs, together with expected timelines. In addition, it recorded feedback from

D5.3- INHERIT pilots' execution documentation –full pilot operation phase service providers regarding data availability and technical requirements. Overall, the tool served as an overview of pilot readiness and deployment progress across services.

Figure 5–13 provide a synthetic overview of the service deployment status across all pilots and services, capturing key aspects such as testing progress, operational readiness, and planned next steps. The tables enable a horizontal analysis of deployment dynamics across WP5. A traffic-light colour system is used to facilitate interpretation of the implementation status. Activities and services that are progressing according to schedule and are successfully advancing towards implementation are highlighted in **green color**. Services and activities that are partially completed, progressing more slowly than expected, or still require additional input data are highlighted in **yellow color**. Finally, services and activities that are currently at risk, with significant delays or major data gaps, are highlighted in **red color**.

REGEA Pilot 1 CROATIA			
Service Nr.	Training Completed	Feedback Received	Next Steps in the Implementation
S.0	No	Pilot Feedback: The service is not in use.	1) Check with SP for missing data. 2) Confirm training timeline. 3) Service under development (expected early 2026).
S.3	Yes	Pilot Feedback: Training for the service was help in January 2026. The tool has been filled out by the pilot and feedback has been given to the SP.	No further action at this stage, as the SP provider has received the feedback.
S.4	Yes	Pilot Feedback: The service is fully operational at this stage.	1) Use continuously. 2) Provide regular feedback.
S.5	Yes	Pilot Feedback: The service is fully operational at this stage. Training session was held in February 2026 with the pilot representatives.	1) Use continuously. 2) Provide regular feedback.
S.10	No	SP Feedback: The service is currently under development and not ready for pilot testing. Delays were observed due to limited data availability and methodological adjustments. Pilot training is forseen for April 2026.	Pilot is awaiting the completion of the development of the service by April 2026.

Figure 5 Service Deployment Monitoring Table (Pilot 1)

D5.3- INHERIT pilots' execution documentation –full pilot operation phase

BOUYGES Pilot 2 FRANCE			
Service Nr.	Training Completed	Feedback Received	Next Steps in the Implementation
S.0	No	Pilot Feedback: Service not started.	1) Check with SP for missing data. 2) Confirm training timeline. 3) Service under development (expected early 2026).
S.2	No	Pilot Feedback: High data requirements. Waiting for results.	1) Confirm training timeline. 2) Align with SP on results timeline. 3) Continue service development.
S.3	Yes	Pilot Feedback: Training completed. Tool filled. Feedback provided to SP.	No further action at this stage, as the SP provider has received the feedback.

Figure 6 Service Deployment Monitoring Table (Pilot 2)

ELLET PILOT 3 GREECE			
Service Nr.	Training Completed	Feedback Received	Next Steps in the Implementation
S.0	No	Pilot Feedback: Service not started.	1) Check with SP for missing data. 2) Confirm training timeline. 3) Service under development (expected early 2026).
S.3	Yes	Pilot Feedback: Training completed in January 2026. Feedback is very positive.	Provide feedback to SP.
S.4	Yes	Pilot Feedback: Very good.	1) Use continuously. 2) Provide regular feedback.
S.5	Yes	Pilot Feedback: Fully operational. Feedback is very positive.	1) Use continuously. 2) Provide regular feedback.
S.7	No	Pilot Feedback: Not started. SP Feedback: Training planned after March 2026.	1) Check with SP for any missing inputs. 2) Confirm training timeline. 3) Training expected early 2026.
S.9	Yes	Pilot Feedback: Feedback will be provided on building techniques. SP Feedback: Fully operational. Additional feedback required through questionnaire.	1) Use continuously. 2) Provide regular feedback.

Figure 7 Service Deployment Monitoring Table (Pilot 3)

D5.3- INHERIT pilots' execution documentation –full pilot operation phase

RPR PILOT 4 LATVIA			
Service Nr.	Training Completed	Feedback Received	Next Steps in the Implementation
S.0	No	Pilot Feedback: Service not in use.	1) Check with SP for missing data. 2) Confirm training timeline. 3) Service under development (expected early 2026).
S.2	No	Pilot Feedback: Service not in use.	1) Check with SP if any inputs are needed. 2) Confirm training timeline. 3) Await service development.
S.3	Yes	Pilot Feedback: Training completed in January 2026. Service to be used.	1) Use the tool. 2) Provide feedback to SP.
S.4	Yes	Pilot Feedback: Service in use. Performance very good.	1) Use continuously. 2) Provide regular feedback.
S.9	Yes	Pilot Feedback: Test version presented. Waiting for real pilot data. SP Feedback: Data under construction. Additional feedback required through questionnaire.	1) Check with SP timeline for pilot data integration. 2) Provide feedback to SP.

Figure 8 Service Deployment Monitoring Table (Pilot 4)

FASADA PILOT 5 POLAND			
Service Nr.	Training Completed	Feedback Received	Next Steps in the Implementation
S.0	No	Pilot Feedback: Service not in use.	1) Check with SP for missing data. 2) Confirm training timeline. 3) Service under development (expected early 2026).
S.1	No	Pilot Feedback: Possible need for model adjustment. SP Feedback: All data provided. Service under development. Training planned for March/April 2026.	1) Define timeline for model adjustment. 2) Use continuously. 3) Provide feedback.
S.3	Yes	SP Feedback: Training completed in January 2026.	1) Use the tool. 2) Provide feedback.
S.6	No	Pilot Feedback: All data delivered. SP Feedback: No issues identified. Training planned for early 2026.	1) Use the service. 2) Provide feedback.
S.8	No	Pilot Feedback: All data delivered. SP Feedback: Training planned for early 2026.	1) Use the service. 2) Provide feedback.

Figure 9 Service Deployment Monitoring Table (Pilot 5)

D5.3- INHERIT pilots' execution documentation –full pilot operation phase

CARTIF PILOT 6 SPAIN			
Service Nr.	Training Completed	Feedback Received	Next Steps in the Implementation
S.0	No	Pilot Feedback: Service not in use.	1) Check with SP for missing data. 2) Confirm training timeline. 3) Service under development (expected early 2026).
S.1	No	Pilot Feedback: Stable version pending. H-BIM integration ongoing. SP Feedback: H-BIM model provided by the end of 2025. Service under development. Pilot needs to provide input on renovation measures.	1) Provide H-BIM model to SP. 2) Provide input on renovation measures. 3) Await service development.
S.3	Yes	SP Feedback: Training completed in January 2026.	1) Use the tool early in 2026. 2) Provide feedback.
S.6	No	Pilot Feedback: Stable version pending. H-BIM integration ongoing. SP Feedback: H-BIM model provided by the end of 2025.	1) Request delivery of and sensor data. 2) Check with SP on service development status.
S.8	No	Pilot Feedback: Stable version pending. H-BIM model provided by the end of 2025. H-BIM integration ongoing.	1) Await service development. 2) Timeline expected early 2026.

Figure 10 Service Deployment Monitoring Table (Pilot 6)

D5.3- INHERIT pilots' execution documentation –full pilot operation phase

UU PILOT 7 SWEDEN			
Service Nr.	Training Completed	Feedback Received	Next Steps in the Implementation
S.0	No	Pilot Feedback: Service not in use.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Check with SP for missing data. 2) Confirm training timeline. 3) Service under development (expected early 2026).
S.2	No	Pilot Feedback: Data availability issues causing delays. Service will use data for one section of building.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define timeline for obtaining energy use data. 2) Await SP development. 3) Timeline expected early 2026.
S.3	Yes	Pilot Feedback: Moderate success. User interface needs improvement. Service complex to use. Currently applied on one building. Plan to scale to building stock level by spring. Final results expected by end of June.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Continue using the service for building stock. 2) Provide feedback.
S.5	Yes	Pilot Feedback: Data issues causing delays. SP Feedback: Missing sensors. Training held Jan 2026.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define timeline for energy data availability. 2) Assess possibility to change application scope (building vs stock level). 3) Define timeline for sensor installation.
S.9	Yes	Pilot Feedback: Unclear user definition. Data quality concerns. SP Feedback: Fully operational, requires feedback via questionnaire.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Request SP to share preliminary outputs. 2) Define user groups. 3) Validate data. 4) Await SP development. 5) Provide feedback.
S.10	Yes	Pilot Feedback: No visible results. Unclear user definition. SP Feedback: Under development. Delays due to limited data and methodology adjustment.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Request SP to share preliminary outputs. 2) Define user groups. 3) Validate data. 4) Await SP development. 5) Provide feedback.

Figure 11 Service Deployment Monitoring Table (Pilot 7)

D5.3- INHERIT pilots' execution documentation –full pilot operation phase

IBB PILOT 8 TURKEY			
Service Nr.	Training Completed	Feedback Received	Next Steps in the Implementation
S.0	No	Pilot Feedback: Service not in use. SP Feedback: Sensors for people monitoring data not installed.	1) Check with SP for missing data. 2) Provide sensors. 3) Confirm training timeline. 4) Service under development (expected early 2026).
S.2	No	Pilot Feedback: Service not in use.	1) Check with SP if any input is needed. 2) Define training timeline. 3) Await service development.
S.3	Yes	Pilot Feedback: Service not yet in use.	1) Use the service. 2) Provide feedback.
S.7	No	Pilot Feedback: Procurement ongoing and taking longer than expected. Sensors not installed. SP Feedback: Recommended change of sensor type.	1) Purchase and install sensors by March 2026. 2) Organise training after March 2026.
S.10	No	Pilot Feedback: Need to minimise data and obtain geo-data. SP Feedback: Under development. Not ready for testing. Delays due to limited data and methodological adjustments. Training planned March/April 2026.	1) Define required data range with SP. 2) Define timeline for data delivery. 3) Define training timeline. 4) Await service development by March/April 2026.

Figure 12 Service Deployment Monitoring Table (Pilot 8)

D5.3- INHERIT pilots' execution documentation –full pilot operation phase

Service Nr.	Service provider feedback
S.0	Service deployed and in final stage. Data retrieved from all pilots except Pilot 8 due to missing people monitoring sensors. No major issues expected. Training planned early 2026.
S.1	Service under development. All data provided for Pilot 5. Pilot 6 still needs to provide data. Training planned Mar/Apr 2026.
S.2	Service progressing on track. Training planned after validation of energy models.
S.3	Training and implementation started in Jan 2026. Issues identified with UI development and need for expert-driven parameter assessment.
S.4	Fully operational across all pilots. Feedback from pilots required.
S.5	Fully operational in Pilots 1 and 3. Training held in Jan 2026. Feedback required.
S.6	Progress ongoing. Pilot 5 operational with minor issues. Pilot 6 delayed due to BIM and data access. No delays expected.
S.7	Service running on synthetic data. Pilot usage expected around March 2026.
S.8	No delays expected. Service planned for pilot use by April 2026.
S.9	Fully operational in Pilots 3 and 7. Pilot 4 has data issues and requires feedback via questionnaire.
S.10	Under development. Not ready for pilot testing. Delays due to limited data availability and methodological adjustments. Training planned Mar/Apr 2026.

Figure 13 Service Providers Monitoring Table

D5.3- INHERIT pilots' execution documentation –full pilot operation phase

Overall, the full deployment phase served as a validation stage for deployment processes, coordination mechanisms and monitoring practices, and provided critical insights into the practical conditions under which INHERIT services are deployed in diverse cultural heritage settings. Based on the outcomes of Iteration 1, preparatory activities for Iteration 2 will be initiated in March 2026 to capture further progress as services move toward more advanced testing and operational stages.

4.2. Cross-Pilot Deployment Coordination and Support

Cross-pilot deployment coordination was a core activity of Task 5.3 during the full operation phase. Coordination efforts focused on ensuring alignment between pilot partners and service providers, monitoring deployment progress and addressing emerging issues in a timely manner.

During the execution of the full deployment phase, it became evident that pilot engagement and readiness levels varied significantly. While several pilots actively contributed to deployment monitoring and reporting activities, others required additional follow-up and support to ensure timely provision of inputs. In particular, delays in the availability of key technical prerequisites such as BIM or HBIM models or sensors, affected the planned deployment timelines for certain services and necessitated adjustments at WP5 level. These observations highlighted the need for reinforced pilot activation measures beyond what had been anticipated during the planning phase.

To support this process, structured communication mechanisms were established, including regular WP5 meetings, bilateral coordination calls and targeted follow-ups with individual pilots and service providers. A shared tracking table (**Figure 5-Figure 13**) introduced and iteratively updated to collect deployment status information across pilots, covering service readiness, testing progress and outstanding dependencies. To address uneven levels of pilot engagement and ensure continuity of deployment activities, coordination efforts were intensified during the reporting period. In addition to regular WP5 bi-weekly meetings, targeted and pilot-specific communication was implemented. This included individual follow-up emails with clear, tailored instructions outlining expected inputs, deadlines and next steps for each pilot. These targeted coordination actions proved essential in reactivating delayed inputs, clarifying responsibilities and supporting pilots that faced organisational or technical constraints during the deployment phase.

The information summarised in **Figure 5-Figure 13** was collected through a structured monitoring process coordinated under Task 5.3 and further detailed in [Section 4.4](#). The process required iterative data collection and targeted follow-ups to address incomplete submissions and clarify technical dependencies. This coordination process highlighted the importance of proactive engagement with pilots and continuous communication with service providers. Overall, the coordination and support mechanisms proved effective in improving data completeness and enabling a consistent cross-pilot overview of deployment progress.

In parallel, coordination with WP5 leadership and technical teams from WP3 and WP4 was maintained to support issue escalation and resolution when deployment challenges exceeded pilot-level control. This approach enabled cross-WP visibility of critical issues and facilitated prioritised technical support where required.

4.3. Summary of Deployment Actions Across Pilots

Across pilot sites, deployment activities followed a broadly common sequence, despite differences in local conditions and service portfolios. These actions typically included service configuration, preparation or installation of required hardware and software components, initiation of testing activities and validation of data flows.

The cross-pilot overview (**Table 18**) indicated that deployment progress was influenced by several factors, including data availability, readiness of digital building models (e.g. BIM or HBIM), infrastructure constraints typical of heritage buildings, service development timelines, and the organisational readiness of pilots to test and validate the services. These factors led to variations between planned and actual deployment timelines, particularly where pilot-specific inputs were delivered later than anticipated or where service interdependencies affected sequencing. As a result, deviations from the original deployment plan were observed in several cases, requiring adaptive planning, intensified coordination efforts and reinforced WP5-level support to realign deployment actions with the evolving readiness conditions of individual pilots.

To ensure consistent classification across pilots, service deployment stages were defined based on a set of operational criteria agreed within Task 5.3. Services were classified as **development/configuration** when technical preparation activities were still ongoing, such as service development, configuration, or preparation of required digital inputs (e.g., BIM/HBIM models or sensor infrastructure). Services were considered to be in the **testing phase** once pilot-specific data were integrated and initial testing sessions with pilot partners had started. A service was classified as **operational/continuous use** when it was actively used by the pilot and providing regular data outputs or decision-support insights. Finally, **demonstration/training** refers to services that had been presented or tested with pilot teams during dedicated training or onboarding sessions but were not yet fully integrated into daily pilot operation.

The numbers presented in **Table 18** refer to service–pilot implementations rather than distinct services. Since the same service can be deployed at different stages across pilot sites, a single service may appear in more than one deployment stage depending on the pilot context.

Table 18 Cross-pilot overview of service deployment stages

Deployment stage	Number of services	Services
Development / configuration / preparation	6	Service 0 – Smartification & Data Exchange Platform; Service 2 – Modelling and Simulation Environment; Service 3 – Decision Support Tool for Optimal Renovation Planning (in several pilots still in preparation); Service 6 – Digital Twin for heritage facilities' real-time monitoring; Service 8 – Preventive Maintenance with H-BIM; Service 10 – Heritage Building Environmental Climate Scenarios

D5.3- INHERIT pilots' execution documentation –full pilot operation phase

Testing phase	7	Service 1 – Interactive screen use & AR/VR interfaces; Service 2 – Modelling and Simulation Environment; Service 3 – Decision Support Tool for Optimal Renovation Planning; Service 4 – Indoor Environmental Quality & Comfort Optimisation; Service 5 – Energy Forecasting & Data-Driven Intelligent Management; Service 6 – Digital Twin; Service 8 – Preventive Maintenance with H-BIM
Operational / continuous use	4	Service 4 – Indoor Environmental Quality & Comfort Optimisation; Service 5 – Energy Forecasting & Data-Driven Intelligent Management; Service 7 – Real-Time Insights on Activity and Mobility Patterns; Service 9 – GIS-Based Solution for Sustainable Heritage Maintenance
Demonstration / training with pilots	5	Service 1 – AR/VR interfaces; Service 3 – Decision Support Tool; Service 4 – IEQ monitoring; Service 6 – Digital Twin; Service 8 – Preventive Maintenance with H-BIM

The overview presented in **Table 18** illustrates the heterogeneous maturity levels of the INHERIT services during the full deployment phase. Monitoring and data-driven services such as Service 4 (Indoor Environmental Quality monitoring) and Service 5 (Energy forecasting and intelligent management) represent the most advanced implementations, as they have already entered continuous operational use in several pilots. In contrast, services requiring complex modelling inputs or advanced digital assets, such as Service 2 (Modelling and Simulation Environment), Service 6 (Digital Twin) and Service 8 (Preventive Maintenance with H-BIM) remain at earlier deployment stages in several pilots due to dependencies on digital models, sensor infrastructure and service development timelines.

Despite these challenges, significant progress was achieved during the reporting period. Monitoring results collected through the Task 5.3 tracking table indicate measurable progress across several pilots during the reporting period. Deployment progress was assessed against the operational milestones defined for the pilot phase (M14–M27), including pilot readiness, service onboarding, training and the initiation of testing and feedback activities. Several pilots progressed to higher deployment stages following targeted coordination actions under Task 5.3, including additional data collection rounds, bilateral follow-ups with pilots and service providers, and escalation of critical issues through WP5 coordination meetings. For example, the delayed provision of the HBIM model in the Spanish pilot was resolved during the reporting period, enabling service providers to continue service configuration and testing activities. Similarly, follow-up coordination helped clarify service requirements and data inputs in several pilots, while procurement procedures affecting sensor installation in the Turkish pilot and data availability constraints in the Swedish pilot were identified as critical factors affecting deployment timelines. These coordination actions improved data completeness in the monitoring table and supported several pilots in progressing from preparatory stages toward testing and demonstration activities.

4.4. Operational Monitoring Activities

Operational monitoring was implemented as a core management instrument during the full pilot operation phase. Its primary objective was to provide an up-to-date, cross-pilot overview of deployment progress, service readiness and operational status, supporting both coordination and decision-making processes.

In practice, coordination activities during the first monitoring iteration involved continuous interaction with both pilot partners and service providers to collect and validate deployment information. Initial requests for service status updates were sent to service providers in October 2025, followed by a revised monitoring table circulated in December to capture updated inputs. For pilot partners, the first reporting round using the tracking table took place in November 2025; however, several submissions were incomplete or missing. It required a second round of data collection and targeted follow-up communication, especially for those pilots that did not provide input. Additional coordination efforts included bilateral exchanges with specific pilots to clarify dependencies related to digital models, data availability or sensor deployment. In some cases, coordination was also required to address delays in pilot inputs or service provider responses, which were discussed during WP5 coordination meetings and followed up through individual communication with the relevant partners. Following the second data collection round and additional follow-up with pilots, all tracking tables were completed with the required inputs, enabling improved tracking of service deployment across pilots.

This iterative monitoring approach proved critical for improving data reliability and ensuring a consistent cross-pilot overview. Monitoring focused on qualitative and operational indicators, including testing status, data flow reliability, configuration completeness and identification of outstanding dependencies.

The iterative monitoring process enabled gaps, inconsistencies or delays to be detected early and addressed through targeted follow-up actions. Monitoring outputs informed coordination discussions, supported prioritisation of technical support and provided a transparent basis for assessing readiness for subsequent project phases. In this sense, operational monitoring functioned not only as a reporting tool, but also as an active management mechanism within WP5.

4.5. Feedback Loops Between Pilots and Technical Teams

Continuous feedback loops were established to support iterative improvement of both services and deployment processes during the full operation phase. Feedback was collected through coordination calls, testing sessions, bilateral exchanges and structured review of monitoring inputs. Typical feedback themes included service usability during early testing, data quality and continuity issues, infrastructure-related constraints and clarification of technical requirements. Interaction between pilots and service developers further highlighted recurring technical themes, including improved user interface usability and simplification for non-expert users; requests for extended functionalities such as data input, editing and deletion capabilities; challenges related to data availability, integration and interoperability; and the need for clearer user guidance and technical support during service operation. These inputs informed ongoing service refinement and optimisation efforts. Where necessary, feedback was escalated to WP5 leadership and relevant technical teams to facilitate resolution and ensure alignment across project components.

This structured feedback process enabled incremental refinement of service configurations, deployment procedures and coordination practices. It also strengthened mutual understanding

D5.3- INHERIT pilots' execution documentation –full pilot operation phase between pilots and service developers, contributing to more efficient deployment activities and improved readiness for the validation phase.

4.6. Readiness Toward the Final Pilot Validation Phase

By the end of the reporting period, pilots reached different levels of readiness for the final validation phase. In this context, readiness refers to the extent to which services are deployed, tested with users and supported by stable data flows for validation. Higher readiness corresponds to pilots that have reached milestones related to training, testing and initial service use (M25–M27), while lower readiness reflects pilots still addressing earlier prerequisites such as data provision and service onboarding (M14–M22).

Key remaining steps toward the validation phase include consolidation of data flows, completion of scheduled testing activities and continued coordination between pilots and service providers. Identified risks primarily relate to infrastructure constraints, service complexity and interdependencies between technical components, while mitigation actions include continued targeted coordination, follow-ups with pilots and service providers, and support in resolving critical technical prerequisites.

Overall, higher readiness levels were observed in the Croatian, Greek, Latvian and Polish pilots, where several services have progressed to testing or operational use. Medium readiness was identified in the Spanish and French, pilots, where key prerequisites have been progressively addressed and services are entering testing phases, including the provision of the HBIM model in the Spanish pilot, which enabled continuation of service configuration. In contrast, lower readiness levels were observed in the Swedish and Turkish pilots, where deployment is still affected by data availability constraints, service scope clarification issues and delays in sensor procurement.

The full pilot operation phase established a structured and transparent basis for advancing toward the final validation phase, supported by cross-pilot monitoring, coordinated deployment actions and continuous feedback mechanisms at WP5 level. It should be noted that the monitoring methodology, KPIs and coordination framework applied during the full deployment phase were defined in earlier project stages and documented in D5.2. The experience gained during the execution phase confirmed the relevance of this framework, while also revealing the need for stronger pilot activation mechanisms to ensure timely and consistent data provision. These insights are being taken into account in preparation for the final validation phase.

5. Evaluation & Impact Assessment- Interim Progress

5.1. Overview and Purpose of Task 5.5 in the Full Deployment Phase

Task 5.5 is responsible for the structured monitoring and evaluation of the INHERIT solutions during their deployment across the pilot sites. Its primary objective is to assess the performance, relevance and emerging impacts of the services across technical, economic, social and environmental dimensions. The task ensures that evaluation activities evolve in parallel with service implementation, maintaining methodological consistency while adapting to real operational conditions. The methodological foundations of the Evaluation and Impact Assessment Framework were established in D5.2, where the framework was defined, the initial set of KPIs was structured, and baseline conditions were documented for each pilot. In the current full deployment phase, the focus shifts from framework establishment to its systematic application under real implementation conditions.

During this phase, Task 5.5 concentrates on operationalising and consolidating the framework across heterogeneous pilot contexts. As services are implemented at different speeds and levels of maturity, the availability and depth of measurable data varies. The evaluation approach therefore combines quantitative performance monitoring with structured qualitative evidence, ensuring that assessment activities remain proportionate to the stage of deployment of each service.

In this context, Task 5.5 aims to apply and progressively consolidate the evaluation framework, establish consistent monitoring structures across pilots, integrate qualitative insights alongside baseline data, and prepare the methodological foundation for comparative performance and impact assessment in the subsequent post-implementation phase. This phased approach ensures continuity between framework development (D5.2), operational monitoring (D5.3), and final impact consolidation (D5.4).

D5.3- INHERIT pilots' execution documentation –full pilot operation phase

5.2. Progress on Evaluation Framework Implementation

Figure 14 Phased Implementation of the INHERIT Evaluation and Impact Assessment Framework

The Evaluation and Impact Assessment Framework of the INHERIT project is implemented through a structured three-phase approach aligned with the overall pilot deployment timeline. As illustrated in **Figure 14**, the evaluation activities evolve across the pre-implementation, full implementation, and post-implementation stages, corresponding respectively to Deliverables D5.2, D5.3, and D5.4.

The first phase, documented in D5.2, focused on establishing the methodological foundations of the evaluation process. During this stage, the framework established under WP3 was further developed and operationalised for pilot application. The initial set of KPIs was refined, and baseline data were collected for each pilot through Task 5.1 activities. Particular emphasis was placed on structuring the evaluation across the four core dimensions, technical, economic, social, and environmental, while integrating user-related indicators emerging from Task 2.4. A key output of this phase was the development of **the consolidated monitoring Excel tool**. This tool was designed as the central operational instrument of Task 5.5, enabling systematic documentation of baseline values, KPI definitions, pilot-specific indicators, and qualitative inputs. It provides a harmonised structure across all pilots while preserving site-specific characteristics through dedicated worksheets and annotation fields.

The second phase, reflected in the present deliverable (D5.3), marks the transition from framework establishment to its application under real deployment conditions. At this stage, services are in the process of implementation and full performance data are not yet available across all pilots. Consequently, the focus of the assessment is primarily on capturing pilot expectations, perceived strengths, anticipated results, and user perspectives as services are being deployed. The emphasis therefore lies on the social and strategic dimensions of the framework, ensuring that pilot aspirations and intended service contributions are clearly documented. D5.3 should thus be understood as an interim evaluation stage, consolidating qualitative insights and preparing the analytical basis for the comprehensive impact assessment.

The third phase, to be documented in Deliverable **D5.4 – INHERIT impact & social acceptance analysis**, will present the full evaluation of the implemented services once operational results are

D5.3- INHERIT pilots’ execution documentation –full pilot operation phase available. This final stage will integrate validated KPI data with user satisfaction findings and qualitative evidence, enabling structured cross-pilot comparison and consolidated impact assessment across all evaluation dimensions.

In addition to the quantitative KPI monitoring, the Evaluation and Impact Assessment Framework foresees the systematic collection of user and pilot feedback through structured questionnaires and interviews, forming the social dimension of the assessment. Within this context, a SOAR analysis, described in detail in the following sections, was implemented as a structured qualitative instrument to further elaborate pilot responses and capture expectations, perceived value, and strategic aspirations at an early stage of service deployment. Rather than assessing achieved performance, the SOAR exercise documents how pilots conceptualise the intended contribution of each service and the outcomes they anticipate. Within the overall Monitoring and Evaluation Framework, the SOAR analysis serves three interlinked functions. First, it **supports service providers by clarifying pilot- and user-level expectations, perceived strengths, and priority areas for improvement**, thereby informing iterative service refinement. Second, it **offers pilots and users a structured reflection of their aspirations and intended use of the services**, enabling alignment between local objectives and implemented functionalities. Third, and most critically, SOAR acts as a **qualitative benchmark within Task 5.5, allowing subsequent monitoring results and user satisfaction findings to be assessed comparatively** against expressed expectations and aspirations. In the final post-implementation phase (D5.4), these qualitative insights will be analysed alongside quantitative monitoring results to evaluate the extent to which implemented services have met the expectations and strategic ambitions identified at this stage.

5.3. SOAR Analysis – Strategic Input to User Satisfaction and Evaluation

5.3.1. Introduction and Objectives of the SOAR Analysis

The SOAR framework is a strategic, appreciative inquiry tool designed to structure qualitative reflection around existing capacities, emerging opportunities, long-term ambitions, and anticipated outcomes [1]. Unlike deficit-oriented analytical approaches that emphasise weaknesses or risks, SOAR focuses on constructive potential and forward-looking trajectories [2] (**Figure 15**). It is particularly suitable in contexts where the objective is not to diagnose failure, but to understand expectations, perceived value, readiness, and strategic alignment [1].

Figure 15 The SOAR Framework depicted graphically

D5.3- INHERIT pilots' execution documentation –full pilot operation phase

Within the INHERIT project, the SOAR analysis was implemented during the initial phase of service deployment as a structured mechanism for capturing pilot-level strategic input. The purpose of the SOAR analysis was not to assess effectiveness or quantify impact, but rather to document how pilots perceived the services in terms of their existing strengths, potential opportunities, long-term aspirations, and expected results. The framework was selected due to its positive, opportunity-oriented orientation and its suitability for capturing user perspectives within an operational evaluation context [3]. It enables the exploration of current capacities and enabling conditions while explicitly linking them to anticipated outcomes. This characteristic makes it particularly appropriate for early-stage assessment, where the emphasis lies on understanding readiness, expectations, and strategic trajectories rather than evaluating achieved performance.

In applying SOAR within INHERIT, the analytical design explicitly acknowledged the diversity of the services under implementation. The service portfolio spans visualisation and engagement tools, modelling and simulation environments, decision-support systems, operational monitoring platforms, digital twin applications, GIS-based interfaces, and climate scenario intelligence services. Given this heterogeneity, the SOAR framework provided a common analytical lens capable of capturing strategic input across technically diverse services while preserving contextual specificity. The results of the SOAR analysis therefore constitute a structured qualitative baseline that informs the broader monitoring and evaluation activities under WP5, including user satisfaction assessment and cross-pilot comparative analysis.

5.3.2. Methodological Approach

The SOAR analysis followed a structured qualitative methodology designed to ensure transparency, analytical consistency and traceability from raw pilot input to synthesised thematic results. As illustrated in **Figure 16**, the methodological process was organised into four sequential phases, beginning with questionnaire design and data collection and progressing through data structuring, thematic coding and cross-dimensional synthesis.

The methodological architecture was developed around three core principles. First, comparability was ensured by maintaining a common analytical structure across all pilots and services. Second, traceability was preserved by systematically linking all analytical outputs to the original textual responses. Third, transparency was achieved by clearly documenting each analytical step and its underlying assumptions. The following sections describe in detail the four phases employed.

D5.3- INHERIT pilots' execution documentation –full pilot operation phase

Figure 16 Four-phase methodological process of the SOAR analysis implemented in INHERIT

5.3.2.1. Phase A – SOAR Questionnaire Design and Data Collection

The SOAR analysis was based on qualitative data collected through structured questionnaires distributed to pilot partners during the early stage of service deployment. The objective of this

D5.3- INHERIT pilots’ execution documentation –full pilot operation phase phase was to capture pilot perceptions in a systematic yet flexible manner, ensuring that responses reflected both the specific service context and the broader strategic positioning of each pilot site.

The questionnaires (**Table 19**) covered all four SOAR dimensions, namely Strengths, Opportunities, Aspirations, and Results, and were structured around guiding questions designed to elicit reflective, service-specific input. The **Strengths** dimension invited respondents to identify existing capabilities, technical features, contextual assets, or organisational conditions that could support successful service implementation. The **Opportunities** dimension focused on external drivers, enabling conditions, potential synergies and prospects for scaling or further development. The **Aspirations** dimension explored long-term vision, desired transformation trajectories and the strategic contribution of the service to sustainable and inclusive cultural heritage management. Finally, the **Results** dimension addressed anticipated outcomes, expected impacts, potential indicators of success and both qualitative and quantitative improvements foreseen by the pilots.

Table 19 The SOAR questionnaires shared with pilot partners

Strengths	Opportunities	Aspirations	Results
What are the core features and functions that can make this service effective in your pilot heritage building?	What emerging needs or trends (e.g., digitalisation, green transition, adaptive reuse) does this service address?	What is the ideal future state this service aims to help achieve in your pilot (e.g., data-driven renovation, resilient heritage, improved visitor comfort)?	What measurable outcomes (KPIs) should demonstrate the success of this service (e.g., % energy savings, improved IEQ, reduced costs, increased visitors)?
How can it add value to your cultural heritage management compared to existing (similar) solutions?	Which funding programmes or policy initiatives could support or scale its implementation?	How can the service become a reference model or best practice in Europe?	How can qualitative impacts (e.g., user satisfaction, preservation of quality, knowledge sharing) be captured?
Which aspects of the service would be appreciated by users or stakeholders (e.g., reliability, usability, non-intrusiveness)?	What technological advancements (e.g., IoT, AI, digital twins) can be integrated to enhance its impact?	In what ways can it empower decision-makers and build capacity in local authorities or heritage custodians?	What benchmarks or targets will define success across pilots or replications?
What technological, methodological, or data strengths would you like to leverage (e.g., high-quality data, interoperability, AI)?	Are there partnerships or collaborations (with cities, universities, tourism operators) that could extend its reach?	How does it align with the mission and values of sustainable, inclusive, and climate-adaptive heritage management in your area?	How can results be communicated to funders, policymakers, and citizens to show value creation?
How can it contribute to compliance with policy frameworks (e.g., Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD), conservation	What gaps in current heritage management could this service fill at local, regional, or EU level?	What new features, integrations, or expansions could realise their full potential in the next 3–5 years?	How will you ensure continuous improvement and scalability based on monitored results?

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rules, climate adaptation)?

To ensure contextual relevance, the questionnaires were tailored at pilot level in accordance with the implementation roadmap (**Figure 17**). Each pilot received questions only for the services planned for implementation within their site, as defined in the corresponding deployment schedule. This approach ensured that responses were grounded in realistic expectations linked to the planned functionality, maturity level and operational scope of each service.

service number	Brief description	PILOT 1	PILOT 2	PILOT 3	PILOT 4	PILOT 5	PILOT 6	PILOT 7	PILOT 8
s.0	Smartification and data exchange platform	T		T	T	T	T	T	T
s.1	Interactive screen use and AR-VR interfaces for heritage building design and renovation construction					R	T		
s.2	Modelling and simulation environment		T		T			R	T
s.3	Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	T	T	T	R	T	R	T	R
s.4	IEQ and thermal comfort optimization	R		T	T			I	
s.5	Energy forecasting and intelligent management	T		R	I			T	
s.6	Digital Twin for heritage facilities' real-time monitoring and management	I		I	I	R	T		I
s.7	Real-time insights on activity and mobility patterns			T					R
s.8	Preventive maintenance with H-BIM	I		I		T	T		
s.9	GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance			T	R			T	I
s.10	Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios	T						T	R

Figure 17 INHERIT Service Demonstration and Replication Plan, (T) represents the tester pilots and (R) the replicators for each service

All responses were collected in **open-ended, free-text format**. This methodological choice was deliberate, as it allowed pilots to articulate their perspectives without constraint and ensured that context-specific interpretations were preserved in their original form. At this stage, no analytical coding or interpretation was applied.

Following collection, a **dedicated table** was compiled for each pilot, consolidating all responses across services and SOAR dimensions. Each table included the pilot identifier, the service under consideration, the SOAR category, the guiding question and the full response text as provided by the respondent. The purpose of this step was to establish a complete and traceable repository of raw qualitative input prior to any analytical processing **Figure 18** presents an indicative example of one such pilot-level table, illustrating the unprocessed responses exactly as collected. This compilation phase ensured that all original inputs were preserved intact and that the analytical process in subsequent phases could be transparently traced back to the primary source material.

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Pilot	Services to be implemented	Strengths	Opportunities	Aspirations	Results
Pilot 2 - Norder	S.2 Modelling & Simulation Environment (T) - Provides bottom-up simulations to evaluate renovation strategies and assess cost-effective energy measures.	1. If it could manage an asset transformation (ie we can manage the move from offices to accommodation and still have a relevant energy mode) 2. not really useful because we do simulation with current tools 3. relevant for end-users if the tool is easy to use for non expert profil, in taht way they can make their own simulation (if the model is already created) 4. no idea 5. If rules are pre-programmed into the tool to	1. green transition - energy efficiency 2. no idea 3. IoT to have real data and improve the model, AI for machine learning 4. Editor : dassault System 5. if the model is quick to do : it may help non expert building managers to check quickly if there are one or a few solutions that improve easily the energy consumption of the building, while preserving heritage values	1. select quickly the one or few measures to improve energy efficiency 2. no idea 3. if it is easy to use, end-users may be autonomous to use the service 4. It's a classical study that we do when thinking of energy efficiency, not specifically related to inclusion confort or climate change 5. cela aiderait à sensibiliser un plus grand public à des solutions efficaces, si l'outil est très facile à prendre en main par un public non expert, mais s'il faut un travail d'ingénieur la diffusion de	YES = 1. % energy savings, improved IEQ, reduced costs 2. By the user of the tool satisfaction (not the user of the building) 3. the fact that decision-makers choose to adopt the solutions proposed by the tool 4. not easy because it exists an energy simulation tool, so could not be totally new for engineer 5. no idea
	S.3 Decision Support Tool for Optimal Renovation Planning (T) - helps evaluate renovation strategies using reliable data.	1. we can better understand how the building owner or other stakeholders think about the key factor that makes them decide from one measure to another 2. help think out of the box, in the way that multicriteria process obliges not to think about Cost effective solution 3. the tool allow to see other stakeholder think, and this fact is useful for all stakeholder 4. no idea 5. I'm not very competent in policy framework, but if the tool integrates rules from policy it can help choosing measure compliant with policy	1. inclusion and maybe esthetic values 2. no idea 3. maybe, according to the diagnosis and initial main characteristics of the CH building, it can propose pre-programmed weighting scenarios 4. no idea 5. no idea	1. The tool could propose a package of measures according to the weighting of values 2. 3. if proposed package solution are directly understandable and relevant to decision-makers who use the tool 4. The tool allows decision-makers to take into account criteria that are less common (aesthetics, value linked to the NEB), broadening their perspective and the possible solutions to be integrated during the renovation of the CH building. 5. broaden the list of measure, and also having measure with high precision in their scoring	1. Firstly, the application of the solution proposed by the tool and then, of course, the improvement in terms of energy efficiency and confort. 2. no idea 3. 15% improvement in KPIs. Otherwise, it would be interesting to observe the decision-making process thanks to this tool, which provides a shared vision of each stakeholder's objectives. 4. It's not original, but to be convincing, you often have to rely on measured and objective figures, i.e. KPIs. 5. As we are not the owners of the buildings (only the builders), we will not have to monitor the performance of the buildings

Figure 18 Example of pilot-level SOAR response table containing raw, unprocessed free-text responses across services and SOAR dimensions

5.3.2.2. Phase B – Data Structuring and Analytical Organisation

Following the compilation of the raw pilot-level response tables, all qualitative inputs were consolidated into a **centralised analytical Excel environment** developed specifically for the SOAR analysis. The objective of this phase was organisational rather than interpretative. No coding or thematic processing was applied at this stage.

The dataset was structured using consistent analytical fields, namely *Pilot*, *Service*, *SOAR Category*, *Question*, and *Response Text*. This ensured that each response remained fully traceable to its original context while enabling systematic filtering and comparison across analytical variables.

Figure 19 and **Figure 20** presents a snapshot of the consolidated dataset, illustrating how responses were grouped and organised within the central tool.

Pilot	Service	SOAR Category	Question	Response text
Pilot 1	Jastrebar S.10 Heritage Buil	Strengths	1. What are the core features ar	1. The service provides climate risk modelling that identifies the exposure and vulnerability of the heritage building to future climate scenarios.
Pilot 1	Jastrebar S.10 Heritage Buil	Strengths	2. How can it add value to you	2. It integrates climate data with heritage asset information.
Pilot 1	Jastrebar S.10 Heritage Buil	Strengths	3. Which aspects of the service	3. Stakeholders will value its visual, and data-based outputs.
Pilot 1	Jastrebar S.10 Heritage Buil	Strengths	4. What technological, method	4. It should leverage GIS-based mapping.
Pilot 1	Jastrebar S.10 Heritage Buil	Strengths	5. How can it contribute to com	5. It aligns with EU Climate Adaptation Strategy.
Pilot 1	Jastrebar S.10 Heritage Buil	Opportunities	1. What emerging needs or tren	1. The service addresses the growing need to assess and manage climate-related risks to cultural heritage.
Pilot 1	Jastrebar S.10 Heritage Buil	Opportunities	2. Which funding programmes	2. It aligns with the EU Mission on Climate Adaptation, and Horizon Europe programmes.
Pilot 1	Jastrebar S.10 Heritage Buil	Opportunities	3. What technological advances	3. Integration of AI-based modelling, and GIS visualisation tools.
Pilot 1	Jastrebar S.10 Heritage Buil	Opportunities	4. Are there partnerships or coll	4. No at the moment, but collaborations with climate research institutes, universities, and regional authorities could enhance data quality, validation, and replica
Pilot 1	Jastrebar S.10 Heritage Buil	Opportunities	5. What gaps in current heritag	5. It fills the gap in systematic, data-driven assessment of climate risks to heritage buildings.
Pilot 1	Jastrebar S.10 Heritage Buil	Aspirations	1. What is the ideal future state	1. The service aims to enable climate-resilient heritage management.
Pilot 1	Jastrebar S.10 Heritage Buil	Aspirations	2. How can the service become	2. By integrating climate science with heritage management.
Pilot 1	Jastrebar S.10 Heritage Buil	Aspirations	3. In what ways can it empower	3. It empowers decision-makers with clear visualisations.
Pilot 1	Jastrebar S.10 Heritage Buil	Aspirations	4. How does it align with the m	4. By promoting adaptation strategies that protect cultural assets under changing climates.
Pilot 1	Jastrebar S.10 Heritage Buil	Aspirations	5. What new features, integrati	5. Integration with real-time monitoring, and socio-economic vulnerability data.
Pilot 1	Jastrebar S.10 Heritage Buil	Results	1. What measurable outcomes	1. Key outcomes include the number of heritage buildings assessed for climate risk.
Pilot 1	Jastrebar S.10 Heritage Buil	Results	2. How can qualitative impacts	2. Through user satisfaction surveys.
Pilot 1	Jastrebar S.10 Heritage Buil	Results	3. What benchmarks or targets	3. Success will be defined by validated climate risk models applicable across multiple heritage sites.
Pilot 1	Jastrebar S.10 Heritage Buil	Results	4. How can results be communic	4. Results can be presented through policy briefs, interactive GIS dashboards, and visual communication materials.
Pilot 1	Jastrebar S.10 Heritage Buil	Results	5. How will you ensure continu	5. Regular updates of climate data.

Figure 19 Structured SOAR response dataset in the central analytical Excel tool

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Pilot	Se	AR Cate	Question	Response text
Pilot 1	S.10	Strengths	1. What are the core features and functions that can make this service effective in your pilot heritage building?	1. The service provides climate risk modelling that identifies the exposure and vulnerability of the heritage building to future climate scenarios.
Pilot 1	S.10	Strengths	2. How can it add value to you cultural heritage management compared to existing (similar) solutions?	2. It integrates climate data with heritage asset information.
Pilot 1	S.10	Strengths	3. Which aspects of the service would be appreciated by users or stakeholders (e.g., reliability, usability, non-intrusiveness)?	3. Stakeholders will value its visual, and data-based outputs.
Pilot 1	S.10	Strengths	4. What technological, methodological, or data strengths would you like it to leverage (e.g., high-quality data, interoperability, AI)?	4. It should leverage GIS-based mapping.
Pilot 1	S.10	Strengths	5. How can it contribute to compliance with policy frameworks (e.g., EPBD, conservation rules, climate adaptation)?	5. It aligns with EU Climate Adaptation Strategy.

Figure 20 Example of the structured SOAR response dataset for the responses received by Pilot 1 in the strengths category about Service 10

Subsequently, the dataset was further reorganised by service, with each service allocated a dedicated worksheet. This service-level structuring enabled responses from different pilots referring to the same service to be examined collectively. The rationale for this approach was **to establish the service as the primary comparative unit of analysis**, thereby facilitating cross-pilot comparison of perceived strengths, opportunities, aspirations, and expected results. This structured, service-based dataset constituted the analytical foundation for the subsequent thematic coding phase.

5.3.2.3. Phase C – First-Level Thematic Coding

Following the structuring of the dataset in Phase B, the analysis proceeded to first-level thematic coding. This phase marked the transition from data organisation to qualitative interpretation. The objective was to systematically **examine the raw responses and identify the main ideas expressed by the pilots**. The coding process was inductive. No predefined themes were established in advance. Instead, themes were derived directly from the content of the pilot responses. This approach ensured that the analysis remained grounded in the actual language and perspectives of the respondents.

The procedure followed three sequential steps. **In the first step**, each response was read carefully and **key words or key phrases were identified**. These typically referred to core functionalities, perceived added value, expected benefits, or strategic intentions. Only elements that expressed a substantive idea were highlighted. In the **second step**, the **broader meaning of these key phrases was interpreted** within the context of the full response. This step ensured that the coding did not rely on isolated words, but on the intended meaning conveyed by the pilot. In the **third step**, a **concise thematic label was assigned**. This label summarised the **central idea of the response in a consistent and analytically usable form**. This label constitutes what is referred to as a **“theme.”**

Within this analysis, a **theme** is defined **as a short conceptual descriptor representing a recurrent idea found in the pilot responses**. Themes are not direct quotations. They are analytical

D5.3- INHERIT pilots’ execution documentation –full pilot operation phase representations of the underlying concept expressed in the text. Multiple responses expressing similar ideas, even if phrased differently, were assigned the same theme.

The following example illustrates this process. For Pilot 1 (Jastrebarsko), under Service 3 (*Decision Support Tool for Optimal Renovation Planning*), the response to the 1st question on strengths (1. *What are the core features and functions that can make this service effective in your pilot heritage building?*) stated: **“The tool enables comparison of different renovation scenarios considering energy efficiency, cultural value, and cost.”**

During the first step, the key elements identified were **“comparison of renovation scenarios,” “energy efficiency,” “cultural value,”** and **“cost.”** In the second step, the meaning was interpreted as **the ability of the tool to evaluate alternative renovation options using multiple criteria simultaneously.** In the third step, the theme **“Multi-criteria scenario comparison”** was assigned. This theme captures the core concept of the response in a standardised form. If other pilots described similar functionality using different wording, those responses were coded under the same theme.

The same coding procedure was applied systematically **across all pilots, services and SOAR dimensions.** To illustrate how themes were recorded in practice, the Results dimension of Service 1 (Interactive Screen & AR/VR Interfaces) can be considered as an example. **Figure 21** presents a snapshot of this coding outcome within the analytical tool, showing how original response text was systematically linked to a corresponding thematic label. This structure ensured that each theme remained directly traceable to its source response, while enabling comparison across pilots implementing the same service.

The result of this phase was therefore a service-level inventory of first-level themes, derived directly from pilot responses and organised per SOAR dimension. This thematic inventory provided the structured input required for the subsequent phase of thematic harmonisation and clustering.

Service 1: Interactive Screen & AR/VR Interfaces				
Pilot	SOAR Category	Question	Response text	Theme
Pilot 5 – Gdynia	Results	1. What measu	1. Improved communication and understanding between designers, conservation officers, and the pu	Improved communication
Pilot 5 – Gdynia	Results	2. How can qua	2. More inclusive and transparent decision-making process.	Inclusive decision-making
Pilot 5 – Gdynia	Results	3. What bench	3. Higher quality of renovation outcomes thanks to reduced misunderstandings.	Better renovation outcomes
Pilot 5 – Gdynia	Results	4. How can resu	4. Increased public awareness and appreciation of cultural heritage, fostering long-term community engi	Public awareness & engagement
Pilot 5 – Gdynia	Results	5. How will you	NA	
Pilot 6 – Valladolid	Results	1. What measu	1. Number of users, educational activities, and visualisations.	Usage & educational metrics
Pilot 6 – Valladolid	Results	2. How can qua	2. Greater public understanding and appreciation of the heritage site.	Heritage appreciation
Pilot 6 – Valladolid	Results	3. What bench	3. Reusable digital materials for exhibitions and training.	Reusable digital content
Pilot 6 – Valladolid	Results	4. How can resu	4. Clearer communication of project outcomes.	Clear results communication
Pilot 6 – Valladolid	Results	5. How will you	5. Regular content updates to ensure long-term relevance.	Continuous content updates

Figure 21 Example of first-level thematic coding for Service 1 (Interactive Screen & AR/VR Interfaces), Results dimension, showing the linkage between original pilot responses (Pilots 5 and 6) and the assigned thematic labels within the analytical tool

5.3.2.4. Phase D – Thematic Harmonisation, Clustering and Cross-Dimensional Mapping

Following the completion of first-level thematic coding, the analysis proceeded to a second analytical stage aimed at consolidating and structuring the thematic landscape. This phase sought to enhance internal consistency, reduce semantic fragmentation and enable higher-order synthesis across pilots and services.

The first step involved **thematic harmonisation.** All first-level themes were reviewed collectively **to identify instances of semantic overlap or terminological variation.** In qualitative datasets of this nature, similar concepts are often expressed using different wording across respondents. Where themes reflected equivalent underlying ideas, terminology was standardised in order to ensure conceptual consistency. This process did not alter the substantive meaning of the original responses;

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rather, it ensured that comparable ideas were treated consistently within the analytical framework. The objective was to preserve analytical richness while avoiding unnecessary duplication or fragmentation of conceptually aligned themes.

The second step consisted of **thematic clustering**. In this context, a **thematic cluster** refers to a **higher-order conceptual category that groups together related first-level themes**. Whereas a first-level theme captures a specific idea derived directly from a response, a cluster represents the broader structural logic connecting several thematically related ideas. To illustrate how thematic clustering was conducted in practice, the example of Service 1 (Interactive Screen & AR/VR Interfaces) can be considered (**Figure 22**).

During first-level coding, several distinct themes were identified across pilots, including “*Research support / data insights*,” “*Use of existing digital assets*,” “*Digital cultural communication*,” “*Cultural digitalisation funding*,” “*Mixed-reality integration*,” “*Public digital heritage tools*,” “*Reusable digital content*,” and “*Continuous content updates*.” These themes originated from different SOAR dimensions (Strengths, Opportunities, and Results) and were expressed using different terminology by Pilots 5 (Gdynia) and 6 (Valladolid).

Service 1: Interactive Screen & AR/VR Interfaces				
Pilot	SOAR Category	Question	Response text	Theme
Pilot 5 – Gdynia	Opportunities	3. What technological advances	3. Information collected from interactive tools can support further research on the preservation and mo	Research support / data insights
Pilot 6 – Valladolid	Strengths	4. What technological, methodo	4. Could build on existing graphic documentation and digital models.	Use of existing digital assets
Pilot 6 – Valladolid	Opportunities	1. What emerging needs or tren	1. Addresses the growing trend of digital communication and cultural education.	Digital cultural communication
Pilot 6 – Valladolid	Opportunities	2. Which funding programmes o	2. Can benefit from regional or EU programmes for cultural digitalisation.	Cultural digitalisation funding
Pilot 6 – Valladolid	Opportunities	3. What technological advances	3. Could integrate mixed-reality or interactive virtual experiences.	Mixed-reality integration
Pilot 6 – Valladolid	Opportunities	5. What gaps in current heritage	5. Fills a current gap in public-oriented digital heritage tools.	Public digital heritage tools
Pilot 6 – Valladolid	Results	3. What benchmarks or targets v	3. Reusable digital materials for exhibitions and training.	Reusable digital content
Pilot 6 – Valladolid	Results	5. How will you ensure continuo	5. Regular content updates to ensure long-term relevance.	Continuous content updates

Figure 22 Example of first-level themes for Service 1 (Interactive Screen & AR/VR Interfaces) grouped under the higher-order thematic cluster “*Digital Transformation & Innovation*,” illustrating the clustering of conceptually related themes across pilots and SOAR

Although these themes appear distinct at first level, they share a common underlying logic. Each refers to the enhancement of heritage management and engagement through digital tools, digital content, or digital innovation mechanisms. When examined conceptually, they collectively reflect a broader orientation toward the integration, expansion, and consolidation of digital solutions within heritage services. For this reason, these themes were grouped under the higher-order **thematic cluster “*Digital Transformation & Innovation*.”** This cluster does not replace the first-level themes; rather, it provides a structural category that captures their shared strategic direction. In other words, while the individual themes describe specific manifestations of digital advancement (such as mixed-reality integration or reusable digital materials), the cluster represents the overarching digital innovation trajectory that connects them. This example demonstrates how clustering moves the analysis from specific coded ideas to broader conceptual patterns, thereby enabling structured comparison and synthesis across pilots and SOAR dimensions.

To enhance traceability and transparency within the analytical tool, each thematic cluster was **assigned a distinct colour code**. This visual coding system was applied consistently across the dataset, allowing users to identify at a glance how first-level themes were linked to higher-order clusters. The colour coding strengthened the navigability of the dataset and ensured that analytical decisions remained transparent. To operationalise this structure, a finalised analytical worksheet was developed for each service within the Excel tool. **Figure 23** presents an example for Service 2

D5.3- INHERIT pilots’ execution documentation –full pilot operation phase (Modelling & Simulation Environment). In this service-level worksheet, each row contains the original pilot response, the assigned first-level theme and the corresponding thematic cluster, visually represented through colour coding. This layout ensures that the progression from raw qualitative input to thematic abstraction remains fully transparent.

S.2 Modelling & Simulation Environment					
Pilot	SOAR Categ.	Question	Response text	Theme	
Pilot 2 – Noisiel	Strengths	1. What are the core features?	1. if it could manage an asset transformation (ie we can manage the move from offices to accomodation and still have a relevant energy model)	Adaptive modelling capability	
Pilot 2 – Noisiel	Strengths	2. How can it add value to the building?	2. not really useful because we do simulation with currant tools	Low added value vs existing tools	
Pilot 2 – Noisiel	Strengths	3. Which aspects of the service are most valuable for you?	3. relevant for end-users if the tool is easy to use for non expert profil , in that way they can make their own simulation (if the model is already created)	User-friendly modelling	
Pilot 2 – Noisiel	Strengths	4. What technological, methodological or other aspects are most interesting for you?	4. no idea	NA	
Pilot 2 – Noisiel	Strengths	5. How can it contribute to the building's energy performance?	5. If rules are pre-programmed into the tool to prevent certain solutions from being tested if they do not comply with local regulations .	Regulation-aware modelling	
Pilot 2 – Noisiel	Opportunities	1. What emerging needs or opportunities do you see?	1. green transition - energy efficiency	Green transition / energy efficiency	
Pilot 2 – Noisiel	Opportunities	2. Which funding programs or initiatives are most relevant for you?	2. no idea	NA	
Pilot 2 – Noisiel	Opportunities	3. What technological advances or innovations are most interesting for you?	3. IoT to have real data and improve the model, AI for machine learning	IoT + AI enhancement	
Pilot 2 – Noisiel	Opportunities	4. Are there partnerships or collaborations that could be beneficial for you?	4. Editor : dassault System	Industry collaboration	
Pilot 2 – Noisiel	Opportunities	5. What gaps in current capabilities do you see?	5. if the model is quick to do : it may help non expert building managers to check quickly if there are one or a few solutions that improve easily the energy consumption of the building, while preserving heritage values	Quick decision support for non-experts	
Pilot 2 – Noisiel	Aspirations	1. What is the ideal future scenario for the building?	1. select quickly the one or few measures to improve energy efficiency	Quick identification of optimal measures	
Pilot 2 – Noisiel	Aspirations	2. How can the service be improved?	2. no idea	NA	
Pilot 2 – Noisiel	Aspirations	3. In what ways can it be used?	3. if it is easy to use, end-users may be autonomous to use the service	End-user autonomy	
Pilot 2 – Noisiel	Aspirations	4. How does it align with the building's goals?	4. it's a classical study that we do when thinking of energy efficiency , not specifically related to inclusion confort or climate change	Traditional energy study view	
Pilot 2 – Noisiel	Aspirations	5. What new features, integrations or capabilities do you see?	5. This would help raise awareness among a wider public about effective solutions if the tool is very easy for non-experts to use, but if it requires engineering expertise, its adoption will be limited.	Public awareness through simplicity	
Pilot 2 – Noisiel	Results	1. What measurable outcomes have you achieved?	YES = 1. % energy savings, improved IEQ, reduced costs	Energy & IEQ performance KPIs	
Pilot 2 – Noisiel	Results	2. How can qualitative impacts be measured?	2. By the user of the tool satisfaction (not the user of the building)	Tool usability satisfaction	
Pilot 2 – Noisiel	Results	3. What benchmarks or targets have you set?	3. the fact that decision-makers choose to adopt the solutions proposed by the tool	Adoption by decision-makers	
Pilot 2 – Noisiel	Results	4. How can results be compared to other services or pilots?	4. not easy because it exists an energy simulation tool , so could not be totally new for engineer	Communication challenge / low novelty	
Pilot 2 – Noisiel	Results	5. How will you ensure continuous improvement?	5. no idea	NA	

Figure 23 Service-level thematic coding matrix for Service 2 (Modelling & Simulation Environment), Pilot 2 (France) illustrating the linkage between original pilot responses, assigned first-level themes, and colour-coded thematic clusters within the central analytical tool

Beyond the identification of clusters, a second-level analytical step was performed. Once clusters were defined, **their distribution across the four SOAR dimensions was systematically examined**. For each service, clusters were mapped against Strengths, Opportunities, Aspirations, and Results in order to determine **where they were most frequently represented**. This cross-dimensional mapping enabled the identification of structural patterns in how pilots perceive each service. It allowed the analysis to determine whether certain clusters are predominantly associated with current capabilities, future-oriented ambitions, anticipated impacts, or enabling opportunities. The lower section of the service-level worksheet summarises this cross-dimensional distribution, providing a structured overview of how thematic clusters are positioned within the SOAR framework (**Figure 24**). This second-level analysis reveals how services are conceptually framed by pilots across the SOAR logic chain, thereby supporting comparative interpretation across services and sites.

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S.2 Modelling & Simulation Environment			
theme clusters for S.2 (all pilots all SOAR)		clusters distributed across SOAR	
Data quality & reliability	Strengths	Opportunities	
Energy / IEQ performance & green transition	Data quality & reliability 6	Energy / IEQ performance & green transition 4	
Scenario testing & flexibility	Scenario testing & flexibility 3	Market positioning & differentiation 1	
Usability, autonomy & user-friendliness	Usability, autonomy & user-friendliness 2	Advanced technologies & data integration 5	
Regulatory & policy alignment	Regulatory & policy alignment 3	Regulatory & policy alignment 3	
Advanced technologies & data integration	Decision-making, trust & capacity-build 1	Scalability, replication & continuous improvement 3	
Decision-making, trust & capacity-building	15	Decision-making, trust & capacity-building 1	
Communication, demonstration & awareness		Usability, autonomy & user- 1	
Market positioning & differentiation		18	
Scalability, replication & continuous improvement			
	Aspirations	Results	
	Data quality & reliability 2	Communication, demonstration & awareness 4	
	Communication, demonstration & awareness 1	Energy / IEQ performance & green transition 4	
	Scalability, replication & continuous in 1	Scenario testing & flexibility 1	
	Regulatory & policy alignment 2	Scalability, replication & continuous improvement 2	
	Decision-making, trust & capacity-build 2	Decision-making, trust & capacity-building 2	
	Usability, autonomy & user-friendliness 4	Usability, autonomy & user- 2	
	Advanced technologies & data integrati 4	Market positioning & differentiation 1	
	Market positioning & differentiation 1	16	
	17		

Figure 24 Finalised service-level analytical worksheet for Service 2 (Modelling & Simulation Environment), presenting thematic clusters (colour-coded) and their distribution across the SOAR dimensions, enabling cross-dimensional synthesis and comparative interpretation.

Responses marked as “NA” or reflecting uncertainty were retained within the dataset for completeness and transparency but were not included in the clustering and mapping analysis. Through this two-level analytical methodology, the SOAR analysis achieves a balance between inductive evidence generation and structured synthesis. First-level themes ensure direct traceability to pilot inputs, while second-level thematic clusters and cross-dimensional mapping enable aggregation, comparison, and strategic interpretation at project level.

The results derived from this methodological process are presented in the following section, where the thematic patterns and cross-dimensional distributions are analysed per service and synthesised across pilots.

5.4. Results

The results of the SOAR analysis are presented **service by service**, synthesising responses collected across all pilots. For each service, findings are structured around the four SOAR dimensions and are communicated through a **combined visual–narrative approach**. Specifically, a graphical representation highlights the **three most frequently occurring thematic clusters per SOAR dimension**, allowing dominant patterns and shared perceptions to be identified at a glance. This visual overview is complemented by a **concise interpretative text** for each service, which contextualises the respondents’ inputs and explains how the identified themes reflect perceived strengths, opportunities, aspirations, and expected results. This approach enables a clear and comparable presentation of outcomes while preserving the richness of stakeholder feedback and

D5.3- INHERIT pilots' execution documentation –full pilot operation phase supporting cross-service interpretation. The following findings represent perceived expectations and anticipated results at an early stage of deployment.

5.4.1. Service 1: Interactive Screen & AR/VR Interfaces

Figure 25 The three most frequently occurring thematic clusters per SOAR dimension for Service 1

Strengths identified for this service are predominantly related to visualisation, understanding, and engagement. Immersive visualisation and interactive representations were consistently recognised as key assets, enabling clearer communication of conservation strategies, renovation scenarios, and heritage narratives. Stakeholders emphasised that these features improve comprehension among non-technical users and support informed dialogue between experts, decision-makers, and the public. The ability to simulate scenarios and present layered information was seen as particularly valuable for early-stage discussions and testing of alternatives.

In terms of opportunities, the service aligns strongly with digital heritage communication, education, and visitor engagement trends. Pilots identified potential for integration with cultural tourism, educational activities, and public-facing heritage platforms. The service was also perceived as a facilitator of collaboration between municipalities, heritage institutions, and research actors, enabling reuse of digital content and strengthening institutional knowledge sharing.

Aspirations expressed by stakeholders focus on inclusivity and long-term integration. There is a clear expectation that interactive and immersive tools should support inclusive participation, particularly in public consultation and awareness-raising processes. Stakeholders also highlighted the importance of embedding the service into routine heritage management and communication practices, supported by regular content updates and scalability across sites.

Reported results indicate early improvements in communication quality and stakeholder engagement. Pilots noted clearer exchanges between technical experts and non-expert audiences, increased public understanding of heritage interventions, and enhanced visibility of project outcomes. While quantitative indicators are still limited, the service is perceived as well positioned to support future measurement of user engagement, content reuse, and participation levels.

5.4.2. Service 2: Modelling & Simulation Environment

Figure 26 The three most frequently occurring thematic clusters per SOAR dimension for Service 2

Strengths identified for this service are primarily associated with **scenario-based energy and indoor climate modelling**, supported by reliable, high-quality data and interoperability. Stakeholders highlighted the value of simulating multiple renovation and operational options using real or representative data, enabling informed comparisons of energy performance, costs, and comfort impacts while respecting heritage constraints. The ability to manage uncertainty and align modelling outputs with regulatory frameworks (e.g., EPBD) was also seen as a key asset for building trust in decision-making processes.

In terms of opportunities, the service aligns strongly with **green transition and energy efficiency priorities**, as well as with emerging digital twin and Artificial Intelligence (AI)-enhanced modelling approaches. Respondents identified potential for integration with Internet of Things (IoT) sensors, AI-based forecasting, and broader digital twin environments to improve accuracy and scalability. There is also clear **potential to leverage EU and municipal funding** instruments for energy renovation, and to strengthen collaboration with academic institutions, energy agencies, and local authorities.

Aspirations expressed by stakeholders focus on **usability, autonomy, and trust in evidence-based outcomes**. The service is expected to support rapid identification of effective energy efficiency measures, empower non-expert users through simplified interfaces, and increase confidence in data-driven renovation decisions. In the longer term, stakeholders see potential for the service to act as a European reference for robust, user-friendly modelling that supports sustainable renovation of heritage buildings.

Reported and expected results relate mainly to **measurable improvements in energy and IEQ performance**, supported by both quantitative KPIs and qualitative feedback. Energy savings, reduced operational costs, and improved indoor comfort were identified as key success indicators, complemented by user satisfaction and stakeholder feedback. While challenges remain in demonstrating novelty compared to existing tools, the service is perceived as well positioned to

D5.3- INHERIT pilots' execution documentation –full pilot operation phase support continuous improvement and replication when embedded in routine building management and supported by ongoing data updates.

5.4.3. Service 3: Decision Support Tool for Optimal Renovation Planning

Figure 27 The three most frequently occurring thematic clusters per SOAR dimension for Service 3

Respondents perceived the main strength of Service 3 as its capacity to support **holistic, multi-criteria renovation decision-making** that simultaneously considers energy performance, costs, and cultural heritage values. Stakeholders consistently valued the move beyond cost-driven or energy-only assessments, noting that the service is perceived to enable **transparent comparison of renovation scenarios while respecting heritage significance**. The use of **structured, data-driven methodologies (e.g., Multiple-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA))**, combined with reuse of existing data and models and clear visual outputs, was seen as facilitating **informed dialogue, shared understanding, and policy-compliant decision-making** across diverse stakeholder groups.

Opportunities were mainly associated with the **ongoing digitalisation of heritage renovation planning** and the service's perceived alignment with **EU policy and funding priorities**. Respondents indicated that the service addresses gaps in current practice by embedding heritage considerations within broader sustainability and green transition agendas. Strong perceived potential was identified for further enhancement through **AI, DT, GIS integration, and automated weighting scenarios**, as well as through collaboration with **heritage institutions, municipalities, and research organisations**. These elements were seen as positioning the service well for scaling through EU initiatives such as the **European Green Deal, NEB, Horizon Europe, and LIFE**.

From an aspirational perspective, stakeholders expressed a clear expectation that Service 3 could evolve into a **reference model for conservation-compatible, data-driven renovation planning** in Europe. Respondents envisaged a future in which the service empowers decision-makers with **accessible and understandable outputs**, reducing uncertainty and supporting balanced trade-offs between sustainability, comfort, aesthetics, and cultural value. There was a strong perception that the service could strengthen **institutional capacity**, promote **inclusive and value-based decision-**

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making, and evolve through integration with wider digital ecosystems such as **GIS, real-time monitoring, and AR/VR tools**.

Expected results emphasise **improved quality, transparency, and consistency of renovation decisions**, rather than only isolated technical gains. Quantitative success is associated with energy, cost, and comfort KPIs, as well as measurable improvements (e.g., 15–20% KPI gains), while qualitative value is linked to shared stakeholder understanding, traceable decision processes, and increased trust in outcomes. Communication of results is expected to rely on objective indicators, dashboards, and case studies, with continuous improvement supported through user feedback and iterative refinement of the tool across pilots and future replications.

5.4.4. Service 4: Indoor Environmental Quality & Comfort Optimisation

Figure 28 The three most frequently occurring thematic clusters per SOAR dimension for Service 4

Respondents perceived the core strengths of Service 4 to lie in its ability to support **heritage-sensitive IEQ monitoring and optimisation**. Stakeholders consistently highlighted the value of **targeted thermal and indoor air quality monitoring** that is seen to improve occupant comfort without compromising historic fabric. The use of **non-intrusive sensors, interoperable IEQ–Building Management System (BMS) integration**, and **reliable, high-quality data** was perceived as essential for informed and timely decision-making. Overall, the service was viewed as a robust mechanism for balancing **occupant wellbeing, preventive conservation, and compliance with energy and conservation standards**.

Opportunities were mainly associated with the **ongoing digitalisation of IEQ management** and the service's perceived alignment with **EU policy and funding frameworks**. Respondents indicated that the service addresses a growing demand for **health-focused, data-driven monitoring** in heritage buildings and aligns well with EU initiatives. Stakeholders also identified clear potential for further enhancement through **AI-driven predictive analytics, DT**, and collaboration with **energy agencies, universities, and cultural heritage institutions**, particularly to address existing gaps in **continuous comfort–conservation integration**.

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Aspirations reflect a **shared vision among respondents** of optimised indoor environments that simultaneously support **occupant wellbeing, sustainability, and heritage protection**. Stakeholders expressed the expectation that the service could evolve into a **European reference model**, demonstrating how smart IEQ monitoring can act as an **enabler of conservation rather than a competing objective**. Strong emphasis was placed on **empowering local authorities and heritage custodians** through real-time, evidence-based operational insights, with future development perceived to lie in **predictive control strategies, AI-driven self-correcting systems, and expanded integration with other data sources**.

Anticipated results were primarily associated with **measurable improvements in indoor comfort, air quality, and energy performance**, alongside **high levels of user satisfaction**. Respondents commonly referred to target improvements in the range of **15–20% for key IEQ indicators**, contributions to overall **energy demand reduction**, and **user satisfaction levels approaching 90%**. Results are expected to be communicated through **visual dashboards, policy briefs, and public-facing communication materials**, while **continuous improvement and scalability** are perceived to be ensured through **iterative data analysis, feedback loops, and replication across additional heritage buildings**.

5.4.5. Service 5: Energy Forecasting & Data-Driven Intelligent Management

Figure 29 The three most frequently occurring thematic clusters per SOAR dimension for Service 5

Strengths for this service were **perceived to centre on predictive, data-driven energy intelligence**. Stakeholders consistently highlighted the value of **AI-enabled forecasting, reliable real-time data, and non-intrusive monitoring** for optimising energy performance without compromising **heritage-sensitive indoor conditions**. The capacity to **anticipate energy demand, optimise operational schedules, and support continuous performance improvement** was widely viewed as a key differentiator, particularly in aligning **energy efficiency gains with climate-neutrality objectives and regulatory frameworks such as the EPBD**.

In terms of opportunities, respondents perceived the service as **strongly aligned with broader trends in energy digitalisation, climate neutrality, and smart heritage management**. Strong scaling

D5.3- INHERIT pilots' execution documentation –full pilot operation phase potential was identified through **EU policy and funding pathways**, including the **European Green Deal, REPowerEU, and Horizon Europe climate-neutrality initiatives**. Integration with **advanced AI forecasting models, DT, and IoT-based platforms** was seen as a major opportunity to further enhance predictive accuracy, while **partnerships with energy agencies, utilities, and academic actors** were highlighted as key enablers for wider adoption and institutional uptake.

Aspirations expressed by stakeholders focused on establishing **proactive, climate-neutral, and resource-efficient energy management** for heritage buildings. There was a clear expectation that **predictive analytics would empower decision-makers with actionable insights** for long-term planning, investment prioritisation, and demand flexibility, while maintaining **heritage-compatible indoor conditions**. Over the medium term, the service was envisioned as a **trusted, data-space-compliant platform** capable of integrating renewables, supporting **AI-driven maintenance strategies**, and contributing to **city-scale energy intelligence**.

Expected results were primarily associated with **measurable reductions in energy consumption and operational costs**, typically cited in the range of **15–20%**, alongside **improvements in indoor climate performance**. Qualitative impacts were mainly linked to **user satisfaction, social acceptance of energy interventions, and improved strategic decision-making**. Success was further associated with **replicability across multiple heritage buildings**, effective communication through **dashboards, reports, and policy briefs**, and **continuous refinement of predictive models** through performance monitoring and user feedback, supporting both **scalability and long-term relevance**.

5.4.6. Service 6: Digital Twin for Real-Time Monitoring

Figure 30 The three most frequently occurring thematic clusters per SOAR dimension for Service 6

Strengths for this service were **perceived to centre on real-time digital monitoring and non-intrusive observation of heritage buildings**. Stakeholders highlighted the value of **digital twin-based representations** that build on existing sensor infrastructure to continuously track environmental conditions such as temperature, humidity, air quality, and noise. The ability to **visualise monitoring data in an accessible and user-friendly manner** was widely regarded as a key

D5.3- INHERIT pilots' execution documentation –full pilot operation phase asset, supporting operational understanding and **preventive conservation without physical intervention** in sensitive heritage fabric.

Opportunities were primarily perceived in relation to **replication, capacity-building, and institutional uptake**. Respondents identified strong potential for **scaling the digital twin approach across municipal and heritage-protected building stocks**, reinforcing city-level innovation agendas and smart heritage management strategies. Additional opportunities included **training local professionals in digital conservation tools** and fostering **interdisciplinary collaboration between energy, climate, and heritage experts**, positioning the service as an enabling infrastructure for broader digital transformation.

Aspirations expressed by stakeholders focused on **embedding evidence-based monitoring into routine heritage management and decision-making processes**. The service was envisioned as a tool capable of **empowering cities and heritage custodians to balance conservation and sustainability goals** through transparent, data-driven insights. Respondents also highlighted the importance of **raising awareness of building performance among users and residents**, supporting more informed, inclusive, and proactive heritage management practices.

Reported and expected results emphasised **preventive maintenance and improved operational performance**. Stakeholders associated the service with **reduced maintenance costs through early detection of anomalies**, improved thermal and humidity stability, and enhanced occupant comfort and safety. The ability to **document building conditions over time and communicate them through clear visualisations** was seen as particularly valuable, supporting accountability, continuous improvement, and future benchmarking across comparable heritage contexts.

5.4.7. Service 7: Real-Time Insights on Activity & Mobility Patterns

Figure 31 The three most frequently occurring thematic clusters per SOAR dimension for Service 7

Respondents perceived this service primarily as a **strong operational intelligence tool**, valued for its ability to provide **real-time insights into visitor behaviour, movement patterns, and space use**. Stakeholders highlighted its perceived contribution to **evidence-based decision-making**, particularly for crowd management, safety, accessibility, and optimisation of visitor experience. The

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integration of **IoT sensors and AI-driven analytics** was seen as a key enabler for reliable, timely, and actionable insights that support day-to-day heritage site operations.

Participants associated the service with broader **digitalisation and sustainable tourism trends**, perceiving clear opportunities for **scaling and replication** across museums, exhibitions, and municipal heritage sites. Respondents noted potential alignment with **EU cultural heritage, digital innovation, and smart city funding programmes**, as well as opportunities for **partnerships between tourism operators, municipalities, and technology providers**. The service was also seen as addressing an existing gap in **real-time visitor flow analytics for inclusive and safe heritage management**.

From an aspirational perspective, respondents envisioned the service evolving into a **visitor-centred, smart heritage management solution**, supporting more adaptive programming, improved accessibility, and enhanced safety. Several participants perceived its future potential in becoming a **European reference for digital visitor analytics**, particularly if integrated with **H-BIM DT and IEQ data**. The service was also seen as a means to **empower managers and planners** through actionable analytics for resource allocation and event planning.

In terms of expected results, stakeholders associated success with **high visitor and staff satisfaction**, improved crowd control, and more efficient space utilisation. Respondents perceived value in the ability to **benchmark performance against historical data and international best practices**, while emphasising the importance of **clear dashboards, reports, and institutional communication**. Continuous improvement was viewed as achievable through **iterative refinement of analytics models and replication across additional heritage sites**.

5.4.8. Service 8: Preventive Maintenance with H-BIM

Figure 32 The three most frequently occurring thematic clusters per SOAR dimension for Service 8

The service’s strengths were **perceived to lie in its capacity to centralise technical, material, and conservation-related information within an H-BIM environment**, creating a single, traceable source of truth for heritage assets. Stakeholders highlighted that the integration of geometric data, inspection records, and intervention histories supports **structured and interoperable maintenance**

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planning, reduces duplication of effort, and improves the organisation and traceability of conservation actions. In pilots where an H-BIM model already existed, respondents noted enhanced readiness and the possibility of **immediate operational use for preventive maintenance**.

The service was perceived to respond directly to the **growing need for digitalisation of heritage maintenance management**, with strong potential for replication across municipal and heritage building stocks. Shared H-BIM platforms were seen as enabling **interdisciplinary collaboration** among conservators, architects, engineers, and facility managers. Stakeholders also identified opportunities for future enhancement through **predictive analytics and automated alerts**, strengthening preventive approaches. Alignment with public-sector digital innovation and heritage funding programmes was viewed as a key enabler for wider institutional uptake.

In the longer term, stakeholders expressed aspirations for the service to **embed preventive maintenance as a standard practice in heritage building management**, supporting a shift from reactive to proactive conservation. By centralising heritage knowledge and enabling predictive planning, the service is expected to **empower decision-makers with improved forecasting tools**, increase transparency and accountability in conservation actions, and position pilot sites as **European reference cases for digital conservation and maintenance management**.

Expected results focus on **improved planning effectiveness and transparency**, supported by a complete and accessible digital record of building condition, materials, and interventions. Performance was associated with preventive maintenance KPIs, including the **coverage of documented building elements, prioritisation efficiency, and validation of preventive maintenance plans as best-practice models**. Continuous updates of the H-BIM model were perceived as essential for scalability and long-term value, establishing it as a **living record** that underpins evidence-based heritage management.

5.4.9. Service 9: GIS-Based Solution for Sustainable Heritage Maintenance

Figure 33 The three most frequently occurring thematic clusters per SOAR dimension for Service 9

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The service's main strength was **perceived to lie in its GIS-based spatial decision-support capability**, providing a city-scale, georeferenced overview of heritage assets, their condition, and maintenance needs. Stakeholders highlighted that the clustering of buildings with similar typologies and challenges enables **integrated portfolio-level intelligence**, improves data trust and usability, and supports proactive, evidence-based maintenance planning. This spatial approach was seen as particularly valuable for aligning heritage protection requirements with climate risk awareness and preventive maintenance strategies.

Based on the responses, this service directly relates to the **digitalisation of heritage management**, opening opportunities for city-wide and portfolio-level preventive maintenance strategies. It supports stronger **collaboration between municipalities, heritage authorities, and research institutions**, while aligning with EU and municipal funding schemes for climate-linked renovation and digital heritage management. Integration with AI, DT, and real-time monitoring can further enhance predictive and climate-adaptive maintenance.

In the long term, stakeholders expressed aspirations for the service to function as a **city-scale reference system** for preventive and predictive heritage maintenance. By enabling cross-owner benchmarking, peer learning, and knowledge reuse, it aims to strengthen decision-making capacity, promote evidence-based maintenance guidance, and support climate-adaptive, sustainable heritage management across neighbourhoods and entire urban portfolios.

Expected results focus on **measurable performance and learning impacts**, including cost-reduction through better prioritisation, improved preservation quality, and the creation of shared best practices among similar heritage assets. The service supports transparent communication with policymakers and stakeholders and enables continuous improvement through stakeholder-driven updates, benchmarking, and scalable knowledge transfer across cities.

5.4.10. Service 10: Heritage Buildings Environmental Climate Scenarios

Figure 34 The three most frequently occurring thematic clusters per SOAR dimension for Service 10

Respondents perceived this service as a **robust analytical tool capable of modelling climate-related risks and vulnerabilities affecting heritage buildings**. Its main added value was seen in the

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integration of climate data with heritage asset information, supported by GIS-based visualisation. Stakeholders particularly valued the clarity, transparency, and scientific credibility of the outputs, considering them useful for communicating complex climate risks to decision-makers and non-technical audiences. **Alignment with EU climate adaptation policy frameworks** was also recognised as a key perceived strength.

The service was perceived as highly relevant in response to the growing need for systematic climate risk assessment in heritage management. Respondents associated strong **opportunities with alignment to EU climate adaptation initiatives and funding instruments**, as well as with the potential integration of AI-based modelling and advanced GIS tools. **Collaboration with climate research institutes**, universities, and public authorities was seen as an important opportunity to improve data quality, validation, and transferability. Several respondents highlighted the service's potential to **bridge the gap between strategic climate ambitions and concrete implementation actions**.

Stakeholders expressed aspirations for the service to **support climate-resilient heritage management by embedding climate science into everyday heritage planning practices**. The service was envisioned as a reference approach for integrating risk awareness, adaptation priorities, and preventive actions into decision-making. Respondents also highlighted its potential to **empower decision-makers through accessible visualisations** and improved understanding of climate risks, while aligning with international and local heritage adaptation priorities.

In terms of results, respondents associated success primarily with expanded coverage-namely, **the number of heritage buildings assessed for climate risk**-and with the production of **validated, transferable risk models**. Qualitative value was perceived to lie in improved awareness, better-informed planning, and stronger institutional capacity to address climate risks. **Effective communication of results** was expected through policy briefs, GIS dashboards, and case studies, while continuous improvement was linked to regular updates of climate data and **the extension of modelling to wider heritage networks**.

5.4.11. Summary and Cross-Pilot Insights from the SOAR Analysis

The SOAR analysis presented in this section provides an initial, structured synthesis of pilot and stakeholder expectations at an early stage of service deployment. The responses reveal a high degree of strategic coherence across pilots, with recurring emphasis on data-driven decision support, heritage-sensitive performance optimisation, scalability, and institutional uptake. At the same time, the analysis highlights service-specific nuances linked to pilot contexts, maturity levels, and anticipated use cases. While the main focus of the analysis and the primary differentiator of the results was structured around individual services, it was also considered important to highlight key cross-pilot themes emerging from stakeholder responses. This complementary perspective provides an additional interpretative layer, identifying common priorities and contextual differences across pilots and supporting a broader understanding of stakeholder expectations beyond service-specific findings.

Across several pilots, including **Athens, Jastrebarsko, Valladolid and Gdynia**, stakeholders emphasised the importance of **decision-making support and operational usability**. These pilots highlighted the need for tools capable of translating complex technical data into actionable insights for renovation planning, operational management and long-term heritage preservation. This

D5.3- INHERIT pilots' execution documentation –full pilot operation phase reflects a shared expectation that the INHERIT services should strengthen governance, transparency, and planning processes alongside technical optimisation.

A second recurring theme concerned the **transition from reactive to preventive heritage management**, particularly highlighted in **Visby, Noisiel and Athens**. Stakeholders in these pilots stressed the importance of predictive monitoring, preventive maintenance and structured data management to support long-term preservation strategies and reduce operational risks. This indicates a broader shift toward proactive, data-driven heritage management approaches.

Integration and interoperability also emerged as a key cross-cutting priority. Pilots such as **Athens, Valladolid, İzmir, and Gdynia** emphasised the value of combining multiple data sources, including BIM, IoT sensors, modelling environments, and digital twins, to support holistic building and portfolio-level management. This suggests that stakeholders perceive the value of INHERIT not only in individual services but in their combined application within integrated heritage management workflows.

Differences across pilots were mainly linked to **levels of digital maturity and organisational readiness**. For example, **Athens and İzmir** expressed more advanced expectations related to AI-based analytics, digital twin expansion, and integrated decision-support environments, while **Visby and Noisiel** focused more on foundational improvements in monitoring, documentation and maintenance planning. These variations reflect the diverse operational contexts and starting points of the pilot sites.

Regarding expected outcomes, stakeholders across pilots consistently identified **energy savings, improved indoor environmental quality, enhanced maintenance planning and improved decision-making** as key anticipated results. In addition, **Jastrebarsko, Valladolid and Gdynia** particularly emphasised **replicability and scalability**, highlighting the potential to extend solutions across additional heritage buildings and city-level portfolios.

At this interim stage, the results should be interpreted primarily as a qualitative mapping of perceived strengths, opportunities, aspirations, and intended results, rather than as evidence of achieved performance. As such, the SOAR outcomes offer a consolidated reference point capturing baseline expectations and perceived value, against which subsequent monitoring and evaluation results can be meaningfully contextualised.

5.5. Next Steps Toward Full Evaluation and Impact Assessment

Building on this interim assessment, the Evaluation and Impact Assessment Framework will be fully operationalised during the final phase of the project, once services have reached higher levels of technical maturity and have been fully implemented within the pilot sites. In line with the methodological principles defined in D5.2, forthcoming work under Task 5.5 will focus on consolidating validated KPI results, strengthening economic and technical performance assessment, and integrating structured user satisfaction findings. The enriched monitoring Excel tool will function as the primary analytical instrument for cross-pilot comparison across the four evaluation dimensions. In this context, the SOAR analysis will serve as a qualitative benchmark, enabling systematic comparison between expressed expectations and realised service performance. The final deliverable (D5.4) will therefore provide a consolidated impact and social acceptance assessment, integrating quantitative performance data with qualitative evidence to determine the extent to

D5.3- INHERIT pilots' execution documentation –full pilot operation phase which services have met pilot aspirations, addressed identified needs, and generated measurable and transferable value. This longitudinal perspective will support evidence-based recommendations for replication and scaling beyond the INHERIT pilots.

6. Replication Activities- Initial Actions & Early Findings

6.1. Introduction and Purpose of Replication in the Full Deployment Phase

The INHERIT project seeks to deploy ten services, see **Figure 17**, to at least two pilots each. This deployment is made up of, at a minimum, one initial implementation and one replication. These initial implementations and replications are designed, among other reasons, to help the INHERIT services identify and overcome potential barriers to their replication so they can be applied beyond the project and across the EU. To make this wider dissemination to other buildings or building stocks possible, some features and functionalities of the services may need to be changed or be adapted. Ultimately, each service will need to be evaluated on its own as well as in conjunction with the other services to be able to gain an understanding of which features must be adjusted or adjustable to allow for greater success in its replication. In this chapter, the planning and steps that have so far been taken to facilitate the replication activities of the INHERIT project will be reported.

Task 5.4 “*INHERIT replication across pilots*” aims to replicate the solutions deployed in Task 5.3 across INHERIT’s pilots and beyond. More specifically, the task will aim to adapt and transfer the solutions and lessons learned from one pilot site to other pilot sites and ultimately use that knowledge to enable an EU-wide replication of the project services.

Initial planning for this task had envisioned a number of interviews of different relevant stakeholders at the demonstration pilots both before and during their implementation of the INHERIT services. The goal of these interviews would have been to learn the pilots’ local contexts and determine details that could potentially impact the implementation. Follow-up interviews with the same pilots after the implementation had been completed were also planned to allow for any implementation best practices to be transferred to the replication pilot sites. This interview plan was modified as described below following coordination with Tasks 5.3 and 5.5 to avoid both overlap and duplication of questions being posed to the pilots to help reduce stakeholder engagement fatigue.

The revised planning for gaining details on the pilots before the implementation of the services instead utilized the SOAR survey responses as detailed in [Section 5](#) for Task 5.5. These responses have been evaluated for all pilots to identify, for each service, potential opportunities and challenges that could impact their later replication.

Additionally, both during and following the implementation of the services on the pilots, Task 5.3 will gather data from the pilots to evaluate how the deployment of the services was perceived, what challenges occurred during implementation and their ongoing user experience. This data will also include recommendations from the pilots on how the implementations could be modified to allow for smoother deployment. The data from the pilots on the service implementations and their experiences is being evaluated, together with the findings from Task 5.5’s SOAR questionnaire, to determine how the initially identified opportunities and challenges impacted the replication of the services within the INHERIT project.

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Once all implementations are complete and evaluation of the pilots’ experiences have been reviewed, pilots will be interviewed to gain additional details and recommendations on what can be done for specific services to increase their replicability beyond the INHERIT project.

To summarise, and as shown in **Figure 35** below, the SOAR questionnaire was conducted prior to service implementation, the pilot operation tracking is ongoing during and after implementation and the replication interviews will take place once all services have been implemented.

Figure 35 INHERIT replication pilot contact implementation

6.2. Preparatory Work Completed During the Full Deployment Phase

As noted in [section 6.1](#) above, Tasks 5.3, 5.4 and 5.5 have worked to coordinate the contacts with pilots. Task 5.4 has, in partnership with the other two tasks, developed preliminary interview templates and sought to ensure relevant replication related questions were asked on the SOAR and that pilots are able to identify implementation challenges and give feedback on these challenges within the operational tracking for each pilot. Contact with the service developers on those implementation challenges and the feedback received is also coordinated with Task 5.3 to avoid the duplication of work and contact.

See **Table 20** below for the SOAR questions identified as providing information most relevant to the service replication. The bolded questions, in particular, have been identified as being especially relevant for inclusion in the follow-up interviews and will consider for each service and pilot the results of the SOAR, as detailed in [Section 5.4](#).

Table 20 The SOAR questions related to the replication of the services

Strengths	Q1. What are the core features and functions that can make this service effective in your pilot heritage building?
	Q5. How can it contribute to compliance with policy frameworks (e.g., EPBD, conservation rules, climate adaptation)?
Opportunities	Q2. Which funding programmes or policy initiatives could support or scale its implementation?
	Q4. Are there partnerships or collaborations (with cities, universities, tourism operators) that could extend its reach?

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	Q5. What gaps in current heritage management could this service fill at local, regional, or EU level?
Aspirations	Q2. How can the service become a reference model or best practice in Europe?
	Q4. How does it align with the mission and values of sustainable, inclusive, and climate-adaptive heritage management in your area?
Results	Q4. How can results be communicated to funders, policymakers, and citizens to show value creation?
	Q5. How will you ensure continuous improvement and scalability based on monitored results?

The demonstration and replication plan (**Figure 17**), was not strictly followed by many services during deployment as it became clear that to be able to implement the service on schedule, the replication pilot would need to begin its implementation before the service was fully completed on the demonstration pilot. This resulted in a situation where it was no longer possible to clearly identify or implement replication findings between planned demonstration and replication pilots. That noted, this change was done in acknowledgement that the service replications could not be expected to be a linear process of copying what was done for one pilot and doing the same at another site and that additional time would be needed to account for these differences [4]. The different services of the INHERIT project will be viewed as potential replication solutions that can be arranged in different ways based on the context of the replication application. For instance, some services have been identified as being more, or only, relevant to building stocks rather than individual buildings while other services can potentially function for both categories.

The following parameters have been identified through literature review as being of key importance to the replicability of the services:

Regulatory framework

Different regulatory frameworks across different countries are applied to heritage buildings. These regulations can limit the types of renovation and maintenance measures allowed which can, in turn, limit or change the value of the different INHERIT services. These differences are being evaluated within the pilots where the services are being deployed to help assess what impacts, if any, the different regulatory frameworks the services are being deployed in has on replicability. Given the number of legal frameworks in the EU and the more limited number of pilot legal frameworks, the results will only be indicative of how indifferent a service is to different frameworks, or how easily adapted it may be within different frameworks.

Climatic conditions

Climatic conditions can impact how desirable different INHERIT services may be to different pilots. The spread of the INHERIT buildings across the EU can provide information on if and how the replicability of different services is impacted by the climatic/weather conditions and what adaptations may be needed if they are.

Data availability and quality

As the different services are deployed, they will encounter differences in data availability and quality. This includes the range, details, time interval, accuracy, continuity and credibility of the data. How different services manage these differences in the data will be considered to understand their requirements for replicability and when developing their replication plans.

User practices

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The deployment of the INHERIT services to the different pilots provides valuable information on how the services manage the natural differences in how users interact with and use them. Different buildings have different types of users, ranging from professionals in the heritage field to tenants or casual users. Each of a building's users will have differing expectations of the deployed services as well as differing levels of interaction with them. These interactions are valuable for understanding the potential requirements for local or specific user adaptations of services to allow for greater potential replicability.

Building design and materials

The INHERIT pilots vary widely in their design and construction. The pilot buildings, or building stocks, differ by country, original purpose, the availability of materials and building practices at the time and place of construction. The deployment of the INHERIT services will help identify what ways services are hindered by these differences, if at all, and what adaptations are needed to make the services more replicable.

Buildings' uses

The range of the INHERIT pilots' different current uses will help in understanding and identifying potential replication pathways for services by showing how well the services deployed in different buildings and how well they function. Identified issues during deployment and/or use can then be corrected to allow for greater value across a wider range of building use scenarios and overall broader replicability of a given service.

Existing cultural value of buildings

Any changes to a cultural heritage building can potentially impact its cultural value. The assessment of cultural heritage values of each INHERIT pilot, together with experience gained during deployment and subsequent use, will help in understanding how different services can best be replicated to avoid negatively impacting these values.

6.3. Observations Relevant for Future Replication

The results of the SOAR questionnaire and the operational tracking of the services, while still preliminary, indicate some areas that likely will impact aspects of replicability of different services. The following points lifted in the SOAR have been identified for monitoring and revisiting during the services operations to understand their impacts on the potential replication of the INHERIT services.

Opportunity Question 2: Which funding programmes or policy initiatives could support or scale its implementation?

Funding for replication is likely to be relevant for most, if not all, the INHERIT services, knowing potential sources of this funding is useful in early planning. Before the deployment of the services, the most commonly identified sources of funding and initiatives were all EU level such as the Green Deal, NEB and various Horizon Europe calls. For some services (1, 6, 8), however, the pilots did not have a clear idea on funding sources or supporting initiatives. After deployment, this is a point to revisit to see if any additional, potentially more local, sources of funding or initiatives have been identified by the pilots that would help with service replication.

Opportunity Question 4: Are there partnerships or collaborations (with cities, universities, tourism operators) that could extend its reach?

Identifying and engaging supportive collaborations is very relevant to replication as is sometime crucial to its success. Pilots provided a wide range of general institutions, in particular energy

D5.3- INHERIT pilots' execution documentation –full pilot operation phase agencies, governmental authorities, related professional actors and universities were identified. This is a point to revisit with the pilots following deployment and when developing replication plans to confirm, and potentially expand upon, these initial suggestions.

Aspiration Question 2: How can the service become a reference model or best practice in Europe?

Understanding how pilots believe a service can make itself more replicable is directly useful in replication planning. Before the pilots had directly interacted with services, most suggested that the services aim to become references by demonstrating their usefulness for heritage buildings. This is a point to monitor and revisit with the pilots to see if additional details useful for replication planning have been generated during the deployment and use of the services.

Results Question 4: How can results be communicated to funders, policymakers, and citizens to show value creation?

Knowing how best to provide results and show value creation of a service is useful to that service's future replication. To this end, the pilots provided a list of options relevant to their local situation and to the specific services being deployed there. The results show that, across most services, the use of factsheets and visual dashboards were suggested, for three services (3, 4, 10) policy briefs were suggested. For 6 services (2, 3, 5, 7, 9, 10) some form of workshop or publicity event were recommended, with dissemination/demonstration events being noted as particularly valuable to services 2 and 3. These findings will be revisited with pilots during the development of the service replication plans to identify any changes or specific communication means for different services.

Results Question 5: How will you ensure continuous improvement and scalability based on monitored results?

The question of scalability is directly related to INHERIT goals of replication and understanding how pilots plan to ensure both improvement using results from services and scalability is valuable. On this question, before the deployment of the services, some pilots were not able to identify how they would do these for some services and most other pilots gave only very general suggestions, such as via communication with stakeholders or that a service might potentially be scaled/replicated to another site or building. The responses to this question indicate that the pilots, prior to service deployments, were not always clear on how they would use the results from the services nor how the services could be scaled before they had been given a chance to fully interact with them. This question has been identified as a key point for follow-up during interviews with the pilots to elicit more concrete responses which can be employed in replication planning.

6.4. Replication Roadmap and Next Steps

Once the service implementations are complete for all pilots and services, Task 5.4 will review the operational tracking together and SOAR responses with Tasks 5.3 and 5.5 to decide which pilots and service providers to interview related to the identified replication challenges and opportunities. Preliminary follow-up questions for each service have been developed but will need to be tailored for the challenges and opportunities of that service and will be developed in collaboration with Tasks 5.3 and 5.5 to avoid duplication of effort. Once the questions have been agreed upon, interviews with selected pilots and services will begin in April and conclude in late 2026.

The results of these interviews, together with the findings of the SOAR and pilot tracking responses, as well as feedback from the service providers, will be used to suggest potential local customizations that can be applied to increase the replicability of each service while highlighting the services' benefits, support needs (e.g., data requirements), and successful applications. Further, using the same information, as well as data on the pilots, the characteristics of the target that are likely

D5.3- INHERIT pilots' execution documentation –full pilot operation phase needed for the replication to be successful will be identified, such as noted above in [Section 2](#) (e.g., building material, building uses or a given regulatory framework).

Conclusions

The full pilot operation phase has demonstrated that deploying integrated digital services in cultural heritage contexts requires adaptive coordination, continuous monitoring and strong stakeholder alignment. While D5.2 focused on preparation and planning, D5.3 confirms that real-life execution introduces variability in readiness levels, infrastructure constraints, data availability and organisational capacity.

Despite heterogeneity across pilots, significant progress has been achieved. Several services advanced to demonstration, testing, or continuous operational use, while others completed critical prerequisites required for full validation in early 2026. The structured cross-pilot monitoring table and iterative coordination mechanisms proved essential in identifying delays, resolving bottlenecks, and reinforcing pilot engagement. Stakeholder engagement during deployment validated the collaborative governance model established earlier in the project. Social Labs, MSF activities, co-creation workshops, and continuous dialogue platforms ensured that services remained aligned with user needs and institutional realities. The transition from exploratory dialogue to more actionable co-production steps has strengthened the foundations for final validation and exploitation.

From an evaluation perspective, the SOAR analysis provided a strategic qualitative benchmark capturing pilot expectations, perceived strengths, and anticipated impacts. At this stage, findings reflect intended value rather than achieved performance. The next phase will enable systematic comparison between expressed aspirations and validated KPI results. Replication observations highlight that transferability depends on contextual parameters such as regulatory frameworks, climatic conditions, data quality, building typologies, and user practices. The replication pathway has therefore evolved from a linear demonstration–replication model to a more flexible, context-sensitive adaptation logic.

Looking ahead, the next phase will focus on completing outstanding technical prerequisites across pilots, consolidating stable data flows and KPI measurements, and conducting final validation and user testing activities. In parallel, structured replication interviews will be launched and quantitative performance results will be integrated with the qualitative benchmarks established during this phase, culminating in a consolidated impact and social acceptance assessment in D5.4. The experience gained during the full deployment phase confirms that INHERIT services are technically viable and strategically relevant, while also demonstrating the importance of adaptive governance and iterative monitoring. D5.3 therefore provides a transparent and robust bridge between planning and final impact consolidation, ensuring that the project enters the validation phase on a structured and evidence-informed basis.

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